

4.7 “Cross-Cutting Topics”: A Collection of Practice Abstracts

A total of 28 Practice Abstracts are categorised under Cross-Cutting Topics. These Practice Abstracts are diverse and cover a wide range of themes, presenting relevant insights into various aspects of climate-smart farming, farm demonstrations, and their broader impacts. The heterogeneity of the PAs reflects the interdisciplinary nature of the project, addressing multiple dimensions of sustainable farming and climate mitigation and adaptation.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #1**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

Reducing Greenhouse Gas and Ammonia Emissions from Cattle Housing

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

All countries and climatic zones in Europe

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE – ADD KEYWORDS

1. Emission mitigation
2. Increased animal welfare
3. Increased resilience to extreme weather conditions (e.g. heatwaves)

PRODUCTION SYSTEM (IF RELEVANT)

Dairy and beef cattle

THEMATIC AREA

Manure storage and spreading

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Reducing emissions from barns is a key environmental and welfare goal. Cattle housings emit methane (CH₄), ammonia (NH₃), and nitrous oxide (N₂O), in large part due to manure. NH₃ volatilizes easily due to soluble N and pH > 7.

Barn Emissions: Key Factors

1. Housing and Floors

- In loose housing, bedding reduces NH_3 but may increase N_2O due to nitrification and denitrification
- Solid and slatted floors have similar emissions; earthen floors have the highest N_2O emissions

2. Environment

- On average, NH_3 rise by ~ 0.037 g/livestock unit/day for each $+1^\circ\text{C}$ temperature increase (See Çinar et al. (2023))
- Farms in wet climates emit less NH_3 than those in dry climates

3. Diet

- Overfeeding protein increases N excretion, mostly as urea, causing NH_3 and N_2O emissions. Dairy cattle generally emit more N_2O than beef cattle due to high N diet
- Low starch increases N losses; balanced energy-protein ratios reduce emissions.

Recommendations for Farmers

1. Optimized Barns

- Avoid earthen floors; solid/slatted floors are equally viable if kept sufficiently clean
- Cubicles with frequent manure removal, minimizing the time the urease enzyme of the feces converts urine urea to NH_3 , balance emissions and operations (see videos)
- Use animal-friendly cleaning to increase cleaning and minimize injury
- Minimize barn manure storage to lower CH_4

2. Climate Control

- Maintain good control over energy consumption (except for natural ventilation) to keep a low carbon footprint
- Insulate roofs and provide shade to reduce heat in summer
- Focus on NH_3 mitigation and N_2O reduction in dry and wet climates respectively

3. Adjust Diets

- Reduce protein (CP) to 12–14% for dairy cattle and 10–12% for beef cattle, ensuring balanced energy and aminoacids
- Adopt precision feeding to match CP intake to herd needs
- Use high-quality forage and test feed regularly to ensure high N assimilation and digestibility, reducing N and CH_4 emissions.

LONGER DESCRIPTION

Reducing emissions from cattle barns is crucial for mitigating climate change and meeting environmental policy goals. Animal housings are major sources of methane (CH₄), ammonia (NH₃), and nitrous oxide (N₂O), the latter two coming primarily from manure. NH₃ volatilizes easily due to manure's soluble nitrogen and above-neutral pH.

Key Factors Influencing Emissions

1. Housing Systems

- In loose housings, deep litter bedding reduces NH₃ emissions but may increase N₂O due to nitrification and denitrification.
- Cubicle housings are recommended for balancing emissions and operational efficiency, provided frequent manure removal and cleaning practices are implemented.

2. Floor Types

- Solid and slatted floors have comparable emissions, making either a viable option depending on farm logistics and operations.
- Different mitigation measures exist for different floors. A common operating principle is promptly draining the liquid phase, minimizing the time the urease enzyme of the feces hydrolyses the urine's urea to NH₃ (see videos).
- Earthen floors originate the highest N₂O emissions.

3. Environmental Conditions

- On average at global level, NH₃ emissions rise by ~0.037 g/livestock unit/day for each 1°C increase in barn temperature. For 100 livestock units (LU), this adds 3.7 g/day per 1°C.
- Farms in wet climates tend to emit less NH₃ compared to dry climates. Tailored mitigation strategies are necessary for different climates.

4. Animal Diets

- Overfeeding CP increases N excretion, increasing NH₃ and N₂O emissions. Dairy cattle generally emit more N₂O than beef cattle due to higher dietary N
- Ensuring a balanced energy-to-protein ratio can mitigate emissions by enhancing N assimilation. For instance, insufficient dietary starch can lead to higher nitrogen losses and indirectly higher NH₃ and N₂O emissions.

Recommendations for Farmers to reduce ammonia (NH₃) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from cattle housings

1. Optimize Housing and Flooring

- For cubicle housing, prioritize regular manure removal to limit anaerobic decomposition and reduce N₂O and NH₃ emissions.
- For loose housing, use sufficient bedding material and remove saturated bedding promptly to minimize N₂O emissions.
- Avoid earthen floors; solid or slatted floors are viable depending on farm logistics.
- Frequent manure removal reduces the ammonia pool available for volatilization. This is done by varying the cleaning frequency of manure scrapers or cleaning robots, although this can come with some risk of injury to the animals. Use animal-friendly cleaning systems (e.g., low V-blade scrapers, robots with appropriate sensing technologies).

2. Enhance Climate Control and adopt climate-specific strategies

- Install fans and/or misting systems to maintain barn temperatures as close as possible to the optimal ranges for emissions and animal welfare (10-20 °C), especially during summer or in warm climates.
- Automated climate control systems help maintain steady conditions, reducing emission spikes during heatwaves.
- Ensure barns are well ventilated to minimize heat accumulation.
- Provide shade or insulate roofs to reduce the heat load in barns, especially in regions with high solar radiation.
- In temperate dry regions, focus mostly on solutions to mitigate NH₃ volatilization. In wetter climates, target mostly practices that reduce N₂O emissions (e.g., preventing anaerobic conditions and increasing the removal frequency and aeration of manure).

3. Adjust Animal Diets

- Reduce crude protein (CP) levels to 12–14% for dairy cattle and 10–12% for beef cattle, ensuring balanced energy and amino acids. Studies show a 15–20% reduction in nitrogen excretion when CP is reduced from 18% to 14% in dairy cow diets.
- Use high-quality forages and test feed regularly to optimize protein levels.
- Adopt precision feeding strategies: divide the herd into groups based on nutrient requirements, allowing precise CP intake to match specific needs, including rumen-protected amino acids, to optimize N absorption and minimize N excretion.

Recommendations for Farmers to reduce methane (CH₄) emissions from cattle housing

Housing CH₄ emissions mainly originate from the enteric fermentation taking place in the animals. The housing itself has effect mostly on manure-related CH₄ emissions.

- Minimize manure storage time in barns and pits.
- Improve feed digestibility to reduce enteric CH₄ emissions.

PHOTOS

Figure 1: Drivers of ammonia emissions in livestock housings. Minimizing the time the urease of the feces hydrolyses the urine's urea is key to reducing the emissions of NH₃. Courtesy of D. Janke (ATB)

Figure 2: Example of cubicle housing with slatted floor. From “Ammoniak-Emissionsminderung – perforierte Böden mit Dichtungsklappen für Milchviehställe“ (KTBL; see videos)

Figure 3: Example of loose housing with earthen floor. Photograph by F. Dragoni

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

Çinar, G., Dragoni, F., Ammon, C., Belik, V., van der Weerden, T. J., Noble, A., ... & Amon, B. (2023). Effects of environmental and housing system factors on ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions from cattle barns: A meta-analysis of a global data collation. *Waste Management*, 172, 60-70.

URL:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.09.007>

Title/Description

The terms used are consistent with the glossary of the Recycling Agricultural, Municipal and Industrial Residues in Agriculture Network (RAMIRAN):

URL:

https://ramiran.uvlf.sk/doc11/RAMIRAN%20Glossary_2011.pdf

Title/Description

EmiMin project - Ammonia emission reduction - flooring for solid paved dairy barns - Video

URL:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MrOxXbQtso8>

Title/Description

EmiMin project - Ammonia emission reduction - perforated floors with slit sealing flaps for dairy barns Video

URL:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XTb4_eyesf4

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #3

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Thematic Online Events to Boost Knowledge Exchange on Climate Smart Farming and Advice Across Europe.

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE – ADD KEYWORDS

1. Thematic knowledge exchange
2. Climate Smart Farming
3. Promote Climate Smart Advice

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

To facilitate knowledge exchange on climate smart farming practices and climate smart advice, the ClimateFarmDemo project has identified 19 thematic areas on which good practices can be exchanged between actors across the different national networks. 12 thematic areas focus on adaptation and mitigation of climate change, with topics ranging from energy management, manure management, over crops management and soil health to agroforestry. The other 7 thematic areas focus on agricultural sectors, namely pig, poultry, arable, fruit, vegetable, protein and oil seed, and organic sector.

Each thematic area is represented by a thematic leader, selected based on their expertise on the topic. The thematic leaders are responsible for the organization of online or in-person knowledge exchange events. Together with the Climate Smart Advisors project, which also appointed thematic leaders according to the 12 adaptation and mitigation thematic areas, the aim is to organize least 2 online thematic knowledge exchange events per year. These events can be dedicated to consortium members only or be opened to a wider farmer and advisors' audience. They usually include a presentation of an expert or a testimony from a practitioner combined with

an interactive session to facilitate discussion between the participants and the experts.

The knowledge exchange events are announced:

- on the events calendar on the ClimateFarmDemo website (<https://climatefarmdemo.eu/cfd/en/#/events>),
- through social media and via the external newsletter (subscribe here for receiving the project's newsletter: <https://climatefarmdemo.eu/category/updates/newsletter/>).

The knowledge exchange events are recorded and made publicly available on the FarmDemo YouTube Channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I7Z63eiDNmo&list=PLOYrtkIDkcdTCsFpsc0I8Pq88gMGYLVVV>.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: 12 Adaptation and Mitigation Thematic Areas – Climate Farm Demo

Photo 2: 12 Agricultural Sector Thematic Areas – Climate Farm Demo

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

Climate Farm Demo events calendar

URL:

<https://climatefarmdemo.eu/cfd/en/#/events>

Title/Description

Farm Demo YouTube Channel

URL:

<https://www.youtube.com/@FarmDemo>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #4

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

A Climate Lighthouse Farm Network to Inspire AKIS Actors to Transition to Climate Proof Agricultural Systems

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

EU

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Inspiration for the agricultural actors to transition to climate proof agricultural systems
2. Increased visibility of climate-smart farming practices
3. Improved visibility for Lighthouse farms

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Lighthouse Farms as defined in the Global Network of Lighthouse Farms are “*successful exemplars of disruptively innovative farming systems (...) that are proving to be economically, environmentally and socially sustainable and as such already rising to the multiple challenges of a shared future that is food secure, nutritious, sustainable and resilient* (Valencia, 2022).” Lighthouse Farms aim to inspire all actors in the food system to imagine new visions for the future and are actively participating in research and innovation. Climate Lighthouse Farms are specifically focused on contributing to climate change adaptation and mitigation.

ClimateFarmDemo will develop a network of climate lighthouse farms. The project developed 3 pillars for defining a climate lighthouse farm:

1. **Climate Smart Farming (CSF) System.** They are a front-runner in CSF systems, and they are commercially viable through farming-related activities.
2. **Demonstration and Communication.** They are willing and interested in sharing narratives, pictures, videos about their farming systems to all actors and they are open to hosting visitors on their farm.
3. **Co-innovation and Research.** They are willing to participate in research consortia and projects, publish anonymized data, support master / doctoral studies on their farm, and have knowledge in research co-development.

To develop the network, candidate lighthouse farms will be selected by regional actors in 2025. They will participate in a training program to develop the necessary skills for being a climate lighthouse farm. After training, they can choose to join the climate lighthouse farm network.

Climate lighthouse farms will be connected to the Global Network of Lighthouse Farmers. Two lighthouse farms from this Global Network are a partner in Climate Farm Demo:

- La Junquera in Spain
(<https://www.lighthousefarmnetwork.com/lighthouse-farms/la-junquera>)
- Grand Farm in Austria
(<https://www.lighthousefarmnetwork.com/lighthouse-farms/grand-farm>).

PHOTOS

Figure 1: Icon produced for Lighthouse Farm to be used in Climate Farm Demo project

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

Website of the Global Lighthouse Farm Network.

URL:

<https://www.lighthousefarmnetwork.com/>

Title/Description

Website of Grand Farm

URL:

<https://grandfarm.com/>

Title/Description

Website of La Junquera

URL:

<https://www.lajunquera.com/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #5

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

1500 Pilot Demo Farms are Engaged to Implement Climate Smart Farming Practices and Share their Experiences in the Climate Farm Demo Network

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE – ADD KEYWORDS

1. Accelerated adoption of climate smart farming practices
2. Increased visibility of these practices towards farmers
3. A solid demonstration network available to advisors and farmers beyond the project end

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

An EU-wide network of 1460 pilot demonstrations farms have been set up to accelerate the adoption of Climate Smart Farming (CSF) practices. The network covers 26 EU countries and 4 pedo-climatic areas in Nordic, oceanic, continental and mediterranean clusters. A diversity of agricultural sectors is represented, ranging from animal husbandry and mixed farming systems to specialised arable and horticulture crops, including organic farms. The aim of the Climate Farm Demo network is to:

- increase implementation of climate adaptation and mitigation measures on European farm
- organise 4,500 on-farm demo events reaching 150,000 farmers
- engage 250,000 actors in peer-to-peer learning activities

The farmers will be supported in their endeavours by a Climate Farm Advisors. At the start of the project each Pilot Demo Farm was audited for its climate impact. Based on the audit results, the Climate Farm Advisors and farmers developed a climate adaptation and mitigation plan, which set

the course for implementing climate smart farming practices during the project lifetime. Each year, the farm's progress will be evaluated, and the plans will be updated. In a period of 6 years, each farm will organise 3 demonstration events to showcase their experiences with the implementation of climate smart farming practices with a broader audience of farmers and other stakeholders.

The farms in the network can be consulted on a map on the project's webpage: <https://climatefarmdemo.eu/cfd/en/#/farms>. Farms can be filtered on country, farm type, production system and the thematic areas they are taking measure in. The map is an interesting tool be used by any organisation or person interested in visiting farms engaged in the implementation of climate smart farming practices in their own country or abroad. In this way, the network aims to connect to wider audience outside the consortium.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

An EU-wide network of 1460 pilot demonstration farms have been set up to accelerate the adoption of Climate Smart Farming (CSF) practices. The network covers 26 EU countries and 4 pedo-climatic areas in Nordic, oceanic, continental and mediterranean clusters. A diversity of agricultural sectors is represented, ranging from animal husbandry and mixed farming systems (65% of the farms in the network) to specialised arable (18%) and horticulture crops (17%), including organic farms (28%). The aim of the Climate Farm Demo network is to:

- increase implementation of climate adaptation and mitigation measures on European farm
- organise 4,500 on-farm demo events reaching 150,000 farmers
- engage 250,000 actors in peer-to-peer learning activities

The number of farms per country, differs according to the total carbon emissions produced by agricultural activities in each country. Countries with high emissions (Germany, France, UK, Poland, Spain, and Italy) have recruited approximately 130 farms. Countries with middle high emissions (Belgium, Greece, Ireland, The Netherlands, Romania) recruited approximately 60 farmers. The countries with low emissions recruited 25 farms. The network consists of both commercial pilot demo farms and experimental farms. Out of this group of pilot demonstration farms, a lighthouse farm network will be developed (see Practice Abstract #4).

The farmers will be supported in their endeavours by a Climate Farm Advisors. At the start of the project each Pilot Demo Farm as audited for its

climate impact. Based on the audit results, the Climate Farm Advisors and farmers developed a climate adaptation and mitigation plan, which sets the course for implementing climate smart farming practices in the coming year. The farms show interest in a wide variety of thematic areas, ranging from energy management, over forage production to agroforestry and landscape management. Each year, the farm's progress towards climate smart farming will be evaluated and the plans will be updated. In a period of 6 years, each farm will organise 3 demonstration events to showcase their experiences with the implementation of climate smart farming practices with a broader audience of farmers and other stakeholders.

The farms in the network can be consulted on a map on the project's webpage: <https://climatefarmdemo.eu/cfd/en/#/farms>. Farms can be filtered on country, farm type, production system and the thematic areas they are taking measure in. The map is an interesting tool be used by any organisation or person interested in visiting farms engaged in the implementation of climate smart farming practices in their own country or abroad. In this way, the network aims to connect to wider audience outside the consortium.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: Farm Demo Event in Ireland – CFD Annual Meeting

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)**Title/Description**

Map of pilot demonstration farms engaged in the ClimateFarmDemo network

URL:

<https://climatefarmdemo.eu/cfd/en/#/farms>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #6**SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE**

Minskade miljöpåverkan genom biogasproduktion och efterföljande rötrestbehandling.

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Reduced Environmental Impact through Biogas Production and Subsequent Digestate Treatment

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Sweden, Nordic cluster

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE – ADD KEYWORDS

1. Digestate treatment
2. Improved nutrient recycling
3. Nutrient reallocation

PRODUCTION SYSTEM (IF RELEVANT)

Animal husbandry, Biogas production

THEMATIC AREA

Biogas Production

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Biogasproduktion från gödsel minskar effektivt växthusgasutsläpp inom jordbruket och stödjer en cirkulär ekonomi genom näringsåtervinning, där livscykelanalyser visar en 80 % minskning av utsläppen jämfört med konventionell gödselhantering.

Vidare påpekar Lima et al. (2025) att lämplig hantering och behandling av rötresten ger ytterligare möjligheter att minska miljöpåverkan. Separering av rötresten, där flytgödsel delas upp i en kväverik (N) vätskefraktion och en fosforrik (P) fast fraktion, möjliggör en mer precis näringsanpassning och underlättar omfördelning av den fasta P-rika fraktionen till fosforfattiga fält, vilket minskar näringsförluster och vattenföroreningar.

Studien utvärderade sex olika scenarier för gödselhantering ur ett miljöperspektiv. Dessa inkluderade ett referensscenario, som representerar nuvarande praxis där rötrest sprids lokalt i Kalmarregionen, samt ett Separeringsscenario, där de separerade vätske- och fastfraktionerna också används lokalt. Dessutom undersöktes fyra alternativa scenarier där den fasta fraktionen transporteras till andra regioner.

Studien visar en nettominskning av klimatpåverkan (GWP) med 26,4 % för separeringsscenario jämfört med referensscenario. Dessutom tyder resultaten på att separeringsprocessen kan möjliggöra transport av den fasta fraktionen över avstånd på upp till cirka 250 km utan att öka den miljömässiga belastningen jämfört med referensscenario. Samtidigt möjliggörs en omfördelning av näringsämnen till andra avrinningsområden, vilket bidrar till att minska övergödningen i Östersjön.

Den separeringsmetod som utvärderas i denna studie baseras på pågående försök vid More Biogas AB:s anläggning, där preliminära resultat från separeringseffektivitet uppnådd genom skruvpress och dekantercentrifugbehandlingar har använts. Studien utvärderade även torkning och betonade att valet av uppvärmningsmetod är avgörande för miljöpåverkan och relevans.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Biogas production from manure effectively reduces GHG emissions in agriculture and supports a circular economy through nutrient recycling, with life-cycle assessment (LCA) studies showing an 80% reduction in emissions compared to conventional manure management practices.

Furthermore, Lima et al. (2025) highlights that appropriate handling and treatment of digestate offer additional opportunities to further mitigate environmental impacts. Digestate separation, which divides slurry into an N-rich liquid fraction and a P-rich solid fraction, allows for more precise nutrient application and facilitates the redistribution of the solid P-rich fraction to P-deficient fields, reducing nutrient loss and water contamination.

The study evaluated six manure management scenarios for environmental assessment. These included a Baseline scenario, representing current practices where slurry digestate is applied locally in the Kalmar region, Sweden, and a Separation scenario, where the phase separated liquid and solid fractions are also applied locally. Additionally, four alternative scenarios explored the transport of the solid fraction to other regions.

The study demonstrates a net reduction of 26.4% in climate impact (GWP) for the Separation scenario compared to Baseline. Additionally, the findings suggest that the separation process can facilitate the transport of the solid fraction over distances of up to approximately 250 km without increasing the environmental burden relative to Baseline scenario. Simultaneously, it enables nutrient redistribution to other catchment areas, helping to mitigate eutrophication in the Baltic Sea.

The separation method evaluated in this study is based on ongoing trials at the More Biogas AB plant, utilising preliminary results on separation efficiencies achieved through screw press and decanter centrifuge treatments. The study also evaluated drying, highlighting that the choice of heating method is crucial for environmental impact and relevance.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Referenced publication contains process schemes and graphs.

[\(Comparative analysis of manure treatment scenarios on climate change and eutrophication in the Baltic Sea\)](#)

Equipment used at More Biogas AB plant:

- Stallkamp PSS2.2 – 400 press screw separator ([Stallkamp press screw separators](#))
- Alfa Laval Aldec 30 decanter centrifuge ([ALDEC | Alfa Laval](#))

Publication appendix “Supplementary materials” contains information on waste streams composition, separation efficiency etc. ([1-s2.0-S0921344924006086-mmcl.docx](#))

PHOTOS

Photo 1: Alfa Laval Aldec decanter at More Biogas AB

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)**Title/Description**

Comparative analysis of manure treatment scenarios on climate change and eutrophication in the Baltic Sea

Lima, P.D.M., Edström, M., Aronsson, H., Nordberg, Å., & Sindhøj, E., 2025. Comparative analysis of manure treatment scenarios on climate change and eutrophication in the Baltic Sea. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 212, p. 108017.

URL:

https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921344924006086?ref=pdf_download&fr=RR-2&rr=905fdcf55c91be4e

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #12**SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE**

Réduire les émissions de GES liées au bâtiment en poules pondeuses par la mise en place de pratiques liées aux consommations d'énergie et à la gestion des effluents

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Reducing GHG emissions in laying hens buildings, with practices related to energies consumptions and manure management

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

France, temperate climate

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE – ADD KEYWORDS

1. Reducing GHG emissions
2. Reducing ammonia emissions
3. Improving working conditions

PRODUCTION SYSTEM (IF RELEVANT)

Laying hens

THEMATIC AREA/SECTOR

Poultry productions, Herd management

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

La réglementation européenne fixe des objectifs de réduction des émissions de Gaz à Effet de Serre (GES) de 55% d'ici à 2030 et l'atteinte de la neutralité carbone pour 2050. Chacun des secteurs d'activité doit s'engager dans cette réduction et mettre en place des pratiques pour réduire ses contributions. L'aviculture est un secteur d'élevage particulièrement peu émissif. En France, l'aviculture représente 0,5% des émissions de GES de l'élevage. Les principales sources d'émissions de GES sur une exploitation avicole sont limitées à la fermentation des effluents, à la combustion des énergies fossiles et à la production d'ammoniac (NH₃) qui par recombinaison, donne du protoxyde d'azote (N₂O), un GES au fort pouvoir réchauffant. Des simulations de réduction de l'empreinte carbone de systèmes de poules pondeuses ont été réalisées à l'aide de l'outil CAP'2ER®.

Les consommations d'énergies peuvent être réduites en mettant en place de l'éclairage LED ou en maîtrisant mieux ses consommations grâce à l'installation d'un compteur. Les réductions de GES estimées vont de 0,2 à 2%.

Les pratiques liées à la gestion des effluents sont le pré-séchage des fientes en bâtiment avec évacuation fréquente sur tapis, et la mise en place d'un tunnel de séchage extérieur. Ces techniques permettent de sécher rapidement les fientes, évitant les émissions de polluants atmosphériques, notamment du N₂O ou du NH₃. Les réductions de GES espérées vont 3 à 10% pour le pré-séchage en bâtiment et de 7 à 29% pour le tunnel de séchage extérieur.

Des techniques intermédiaires jouant plutôt sur les émissions de NH₃ ont aussi été simulées, puisqu'elles permettent aussi de réduire les émissions de N₂O. Ce sont le lavage d'air et la brumisation. La mise en place de ces leviers permet de réduire l'empreinte carbone de 2 à 19%.

Ces techniques sont aussi à repositionner dans le contexte de l'exploitation, le système d'élevage (pondeuses en cages ou au sol par ex), et les possibilités d'investissement de l'éleveur.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

European regulations set targets for reducing greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions by 55% by 2030 and to reach carbon neutrality by 2050. Each of

the sectors of activity must commit to this reduction and put in place practices to reduce their contributions. Poultry farming is a particularly low-emission livestock sector. In France, poultry farming accounts for 0.5% of GHG emissions from livestock farming. The main sources of GHG emissions on a poultry farm are limited to the fermentation of manure, the combustion of fossil energies and the production of ammonia which, through recombination, gives nitrous oxide, a GHG with a strong warming power. Simulations have been carried out for the reducing of the carbon footprint of several layers systems, through the tool CAP'2ER®.

Energy consumption can be reduced by installing LED lighting or by better controlling consumption through the installation of a meter. Estimated GHG reductions range from 0.2 to 2%.

Practices related to manure management include the pre-drying of manure in buildings with frequent evacuation on a manure belt, and the installation of an outdoor drying tunnel. These techniques make it possible to quickly dry the droppings, avoiding the emission of atmospheric pollutants, in particular nitrous oxide or ammonia. The expected GHG reductions range from 3 to 10% for pre-drying in buildings and from 7 to 29% for the outdoor drying tunnel.

Intermediate techniques that affect ammonia emissions have also been simulated, since they also reduce nitrous oxide emissions. These are air washing and misting. The implementation of these levers makes it possible to reduce the carbon footprint by 2 to 19%.

These techniques also need to be repositioned in the context of the farm, the farming system (e.g. layers in cages or on the ground), and the farmer's investment possibilities.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

The implementation of such levers must be in accordance with the farmer's objectives and resources.

Please feel free to reach out if you need complementary information. Lots of techniques are also listed in this document:

- *Santonja G.G., Georgitzikis K., Scalet B.M., Montobbio P., Roudier S., Delgado Sancho L., 2017. Best Available Techniques (BAT) Reference Document for the Intensive Rearing of Poultry or Pigs; pp 898. EUR 28674 EN; doi:10.2760/020.*

PHOTOS

Photo 1: A multi-level poultry cage system with mechanisms for collecting eggs and removing manure efficiently.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #13

SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Identificación de recursos, capacidades, colaboraciones e innovaciones en laboratorios vivientes para una agricultura climáticamente inteligente

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Identification of Resources, Capabilities, Collaborations, and Innovations in Living Labs for Climate-Smart Farming

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Spain, Almeria – Mediterranean

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE – ADD KEYWORDS

1. Increase the knowledge and skills of Living Lab actors by exploring, identifying, and fostering future resources and capabilities.
2. Establish and redefine objectives based on available and missing resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations (RCCIs)
3. Facilitate the creation and adoption of climate smart solutions as well as problem solving, innovating, and scaling.

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

Agricultural production systems

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Con el objetivo de ayudar a los Laboratorios vivientes (LLs) a establecer una estrategia común y un plan de acción, CFD ha desarrollado una hoja de ruta basada en cinco pasos:

- 1) La definición de los límites del LL en cuanto a propósito, objetivos, actividades, etc.,
- 2) La identificación del problema central que el LL abordará,
- 3) El análisis de las partes interesadas,
- 4) La identificación de los recursos, capacidades, colaboraciones e innovaciones (RCCI) y la evaluación de las condiciones para crear un LL
- 5) El desarrollo de un plan de acción para abordar las carencias y oportunidades identificadas.

El resultado de seguir esta hoja de ruta es conseguir una estrategia de trabajo y un plan de acción “vivo” y flexible para cada LL.

El paso 4 se llevó a cabo en talleres locales a través de preguntas dirigidas a los actores de cada laboratorio viviente. Estas preguntas exploraban la disponibilidad de recursos tangibles e intangibles, incluidos los recursos humanos, financieros y tecnológicos, así como las capacidades de adaptación y absorción. Además, permitieron evaluar la habilidad del LL para incrementar las capacidades que se identificaron como necesarias. Este paso se centra en fortalecer a los actores de los laboratorios vivientes mediante la identificación y el análisis de recursos, capacidades, colaboraciones e innovaciones (RCCI). El enfoque mejora la comprensión de cómo los recursos y las capacidades influyen en la resolución de problemas, la innovación y la escalabilidad de la agricultura climáticamente inteligente. Se basa en teorías como las capacidades dinámicas y la visión basada en los recursos, la identificación de RCCI permite alinear los objetivos con los recursos disponibles y aquellos que aún faltan. También ayuda a los laboratorios vivientes a establecer planes de acción eficaces para la co-creación, la innovación y la transición hacia prácticas climáticamente inteligentes. Este método cierra la brecha entre las capacidades que se tienen actualmente y los resultados deseados, garantizando estrategias sólidas para hacer frente a los retos climáticos.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

To help Living Labs (LL) set up and develop a common strategy and an action plan, CFD has developed a roadmap. It is based on five steps:

- 1) Defining the boundaries of the LL in terms of purpose, objectives, activities, etc.,
- 2) Identifying the central problem that the LL will address,
- 3) Stakeholder analysis and engagement,
- 4) Identifying resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations (RCCI), and the assessment of conditions for setting up a LL,
- 5) Developing an actionable plan to address the identified gaps and opportunities.

The outcome of this roadmap is a living working strategy and action plan especially tailored for each LL.

Step 4 was carried out in a local workshop for each LL through a series of targeted questions directed at Living Lab actors. These questions explored the availability of tangible and intangible resources, including human, financial, and technological resources, as well as adaptive and absorptive capabilities. Additionally, they assessed the living lab's current ability to scale or identify capabilities that are still needed.

This step focuses on empowering living lab actors by identifying and analysing resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations (RCCI). The approach enhances the understanding of how resources and capabilities influence problem-solving, innovation, and scaling in climate-smart agriculture. Grounded in theories like dynamic capabilities and the resource-based view, RCCI identification supports the alignment of objectives with available and missing resources. It also enables LLs to establish effective action plans for co-creation, innovation, and transitioning to climate-smart practices. This method bridges gaps between current capacities and desired outcomes, ensuring robust strategies for addressing climate challenges.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: University of Almeria – Living Lab Roadmap

Photo 2: Workshop in Almeria - Identifying resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations (RCCI), and the assessment of conditions for setting up a LL

Photo 3: Workshop in Almeria - Identifying resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations (RCCI), and the assessment of conditions for setting up a LL

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #16**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

Agronomic methods for producing productive arable crops with low carbon emissions

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

United Kingdom, NW Europe maritime climate

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE – ADD KEYWORDS

1. Reduce GHG emissions associated with arable crop production
2. Improve nitrogen use efficiency of crop production
3. Reduce energy use associated with cultivations

PRODUCTION SYSTEM (IF RELEVANT)

Arable crop rotations

THEMATIC AREA

Crops Management

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE / ENGLISH

For typical cereal and oilseed rape crops 40-50% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are associated with nitrogen (N) fertiliser, 15% with the application

of organic materials, 13-20% with field operations (such as cultivations), and 12-24% with the decomposition of crop residues.

Nitrogen fertiliser

N fertilizer is the greatest source of GHG emissions for most arable crops. Therefore, approaches that maximise the efficiency of N use and support high crop productivity must be prioritized. These include:

- Create a N management plan
- Cover crops to reduce the risk of nitrate leaching
- Estimate/measure the soil N supply to help estimate how much N fertilizer to apply
- Use N fertilizer products produced with low GHG emissions associated with manufacture
- Use fertilizer efficiency additives including urease/nitrification inhibitors

Cultivations

Cultivations represent between ~5% and ~50% of total GHG emissions per ha. A cultivation system involving plough, power harrow, drill, roll produces >200 kg CO₂/ha on a loam soil. By contrast, direct drilling produces <50 kg CO₂/ha. Soil type has a large effect on GHG emissions, e.g. ploughing clay soil requires 70% more energy than loamy soil.

Adopting low intensity cultivations, e.g. direct drilling, may not be appropriate for all soil types and farming systems. Farmers should introduce new cultivation systems gradually and test they are appropriate for their farm.

Actions

- Prioritise efficient use of N fertilizer
- Adopt low intensity cultivations but take care to ensure they are appropriate for your farm

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE / ENGLISH

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with arable crop production include carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and methane (CH₄). Emissions of these GHGs have been calculated in terms of equivalent (e) emissions of CO₂e after accounting for the greater global warming effects of N₂O and CH₄.

GHG emissions can be separated into seven categories associated with crop production:

1. **field operations** (e.g. cultivations),
2. embedded emissions associated with **seeds sown**,
3. manufacture of **non-nitrogen fertiliser**,
4. manufacture of **agro-chemicals**,
5. manufacture of **nitrogen (N) fertiliser**,
6. **N₂O emissions** associated with N fertiliser and organic material applications
7. **crop residue decomposition** after harvest

Farm operations include the combustion of fossil fuels and electricity used in crop production, e.g., for cultivations, application of crop inputs and grain drying. The manufacture of inputs such as ag-chemicals and non-N fertilisers uses energy and produces CO₂. The manufacture of N fertilisers also produces N₂O emissions through the conversion of ammonia to nitric acid. The application of N fertiliser sources (either organic or synthetic), and decomposition of crop residues left in the field after harvest, produce N₂O emissions as bacteria in the soil mineralises the N.

For typical cereal and oilseed rape crops grown in the UK, 40-50% of GHG emissions are associated with N fertiliser, 15% with the application of organic materials, 13-20% with field operations such as cultivations, and 12-24% associated with the decomposition of crop residues. See Figure 1 for example using winter wheat.

For pulse crops, such as beans or peas, 43% of GHG emissions are associated with field operations and 33% associated with the decomposition of crop residues.

Nitrogen fertiliser

For arable crops, excluding pulses, by far the greatest source of GHG emissions are associated with the use of N fertiliser. Therefore, developing crop management methods that maximise the efficiency of N use whilst also enabling high crop productivity must be prioritized. Approaches for achieving this include:

- Create a N management plan for your crop
- Minimise the risk of nitrate leaching by using cover crops before spring sown crops
- Estimate, or measure, the N supply in the soil to help estimate how much N fertilizer to apply

- Use N fertilizer products with low embedded carbon emissions associated with manufacture
- Appropriate use of fertilizer efficiency additives including urease inhibitors and nitrification inhibitors

Cultivations

Another area where GHG emissions can be potentially reduced is by adopting different cultivation methods. GHG emissions associated with cultivations could represent anything between ~5% and ~50% of total GHG emissions per ha. A cultivation system involving plough, power harrow, drill, and rolling has been estimated to produce GHG emissions of at least 200 kg CO₂e/ha for a loam soil. By contrast, strip tillage or direct drilling has been estimated to produce less than 50 kg CO₂e/ha (Figure 2). Soil type also has a large effect on GHG emissions associated with cultivations, e.g. ploughing clay soil requires 70% more energy than loamy soil.

It should be recognized that adopting low intensity cultivations such as direct drilling may not be appropriate for all soil types and farming systems. Farmers should introduce new cultivation systems gradually and test if they are appropriate for their farm.

Actions

- Prioritise efficient use of N fertilizer to minimize GHG emissions associated with crop production for all crops, except legumes
- Adopting lower intensity cultivations can also reduce GHG emissions for all crops. Any new cultivations should be introduced gradually to make sure they are appropriate for your farm

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

The information for this Practice Abstract was generated by the Yield Enhancement Network project called YEN Zero <https://yen.adas.co.uk/>

PHOTOS

Figure 1. Carbon footprint of typical UK winter wheat crop grown for feed

Figure 2. Estimate of GHG emissions (kg CO₂e/ha) associated with cultivation practices on a loamy soil. Williams et al (2006).

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Visit the website for the Yield Enhancement Network (YEN) to learn more about a network for learning about reducing the carbon footprint of crop production through a network called YEN Zero.

URL:

<https://yen.adas.co.uk/projects/yen-zero>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #31

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Ten Steps to Organising a Demo Event

This Practice Abstract guides National Coordinators and Climate Farm Advisors—regardless of their experience—in planning and delivering a successful demo event.

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Ireland, mild temperate oceanic – PA relevant for all climatic zones

CONTACT

John Greaney (John.greaney@teagasc.ie)

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. To ensure demo events are delivered successfully
2. To make National Coordinators and Climate Farm Advisors aware of the steps involved in delivering demo events
3. To meet the objectives of the event (learning outcomes)

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

All

THEMATIC AREA

All

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Having identified the objectives for your demo event, and established an organizing group, consulted with the host farmer and other stakeholders the next step for the advisor is to consider the various practical steps required to deliver the demo event. This practice abstract will provide guidance to all advisors from registering to reporting on demo events.

1. Step 1. Identifying your focus- define why you are organizing an event
2. Step 2. Build your team- it is impossible to cover all aspects of the farm event by yourself
3. Step 3. Consider you target audience- In the led up to the event you should anticipate who will be the audience
4. Step 4. Select/discuss topics with your host farmer- Ideally the topic is something the farmer has excelled at and will stand out on the day
5. Step 5. Register the event on the project website
6. Step 6. Define your content- Discuss with the farmer. Use research findings to reinforce on farm situations/experiences
7. Step 7. Complete a Health and Safety Check- Walk the farm prior to the event and complete a checklist.
8. Step 8. Ensure you have informative board- Focus on 2-3 learning outcomes/key messages
9. Step 9. Advertise your event with location, time and topics- Local papers/radio, messages to existing clients or farmers in the locality.
10. Step 10. Complete your final checks- sound check, practice dry run, know when to interact with audience at certain stops and identify opportunities to break the groups into small numbers to make farmers more comfortable.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: Farm Demo Event in Ireland

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)**Title/Description**

ClimateFarmDemo- Demo Design Guide for On-farm Demonstrations

URL:

<https://zenodo.org/records/13939148>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #32**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

Involving the Host Farmer in Demo Events

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Ireland, mild temperate oceanic

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Leveraging host farmer experience
2. Facilitating audience–farmer interaction
3. Supporting host farmer comfort and confidence

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

N/A

THEMATIC AREA

N/A

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH**1. How can best use be made of the host farmer's experiences?**

The host farmer should be front and center during a farm event. Ideally, appoint a facilitator to guide the conversation. In discussion with the host farmer, explore the success of climate solutions adopted, issues

encountered, and the pros and cons of technologies used. For example, consider a farmer using protected urea. Ask:

- Where did they first hear about it?
- Did they research it before use?
- Has it changed their previous practices?
- Main advantages/disadvantages?
- Cost–benefit outcome?
- What advice would they give to others?

2. How can you create opportunities for audience involvement?

A farm walk is more impactful when participants can:

- Ask the host farmer questions
 - Share their own experiences
- This may involve allocating time for Q&A, small group discussions, group exercises, or informal knowledge exchange—e.g., over a cup of tea.

3. Is the host farmer comfortable speaking at the event?

Research shows that ‘other farmers’ are a primary source of information for farmers. Whether introverted or extroverted, it’s crucial to assess the host farmer’s comfort level with public speaking. While confident speakers make facilitation easier, it’s not essential. As a facilitator, your role is to guide the conversation, extracting insights and relaying key messages through the farmer.

Events have a greater impact when participants can relate to the host farmer’s system and experience. Ideally, the host farmer should help select the topic, ensuring they are confident and knowledgeable when presenting.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

1. How can best use be made of the host farmer’s experiences?

It is vital the host farmer is placed front and center when hosting an event on farm. Ideally, appoint a facilitator to ask questions of the host farmer. In discussion with the host farmer consider the success of adopting particular climate solutions that have worked well for him/her over the last number of years, problems and solutions encountered on the far, along with the positive and negative side effects of technology.

For example, take a farmer who has started using a different fertilizer product (protected urea) on his/her farm. Talk through the mitigation action with him or her following a series of questions:

1. Where did they first come across the action?
2. Did they do any research on the product before using it on their farm?
3. Has it changed the way they previously farmed?
4. What is the main advantage or disadvantage of using the product?
5. What is the cost benefit?
6. What would you say to someone who has never used the product?

2. How can you create opportunities for audience involvement?

The success of a farm walk can be greatly improved by actively giving participants the opportunity to (1) ask questions of the host farmer and (2) share their experiences with the audience. This might involve allocating adequate time for a “Q&A session” with the host farmer, organising discussions with smaller numbers of participants, organising group exercises with small groups or creating opportunities for more informal knowledge exchange, e.g., over a cup of tea.

3. Is the host farmer comfortable speaking at the event?

All the academic literature suggests ‘other farmers’ are farmers’ most frequently reported sources of information. While it does not make a difference if a farmer is an extrovert or an introvert when it comes to hosting an event on a farm it is extremely important to know how comfortable he/she is with public speaking to relay on-farm messages. Whilst it makes the job of the advisor a lot easier if the farmer in question can handle the pressure of speaking in front of an audience it is not a necessity as it is your job as the facilitator to probe and extract the information, relaying the messages through the farmer in question.

Ensuring farmers can relate their farming system to what the host farmer is trying to achieve has more impact, operating under the same ‘real life’. Ideally the farmer hosting should suggest what they wish to showcase prior to the event as they will ultimately be more comfortable speaking about the topic or measure in question.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: Demo Farm Event in Ireland – Climate Farm Demo

Photo 2: Audience involvement at on-farm event in Ireland

Source: TEAGASC

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

Climate Farm Demo Design Guide

URL:

<https://zenodo.org/records/13939148>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #39

SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Danmark's CO₂-afgift på landbrugsproduktion - hvad betyder det for de danske landmænd?

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Denmark's Carbon Tax – What does it Mean for the Danish Farmers?

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Denmark, north temperate zone

CONTACT

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BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Emissions reduction toward climate neutrality
2. Adoption of sustainable, climate-smart farming
3. Green tax reinvestment in eco-friendly technologies
4. Peatland restoration, afforestation, and carbon conservation

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN DANISH

Danmark er i gang med at implementere den første klimaafgift i verden, der er målrettet landbrugets udledninger. Politikken, som efter planen skal træde i kraft i 2030, er et centralt element i Danmarks klimastrategi og målet om at opnå CO₂-neutralitet i 2050. Nogle af de vigtigste aspekter er:

- **Tidslinje for implementering:** Afgiften vil blive indført i 2030 med en indledende sats på 300 danske kroner (ca. 43 dollars) pr. ton CO₂-ækvivalent udledning. Denne sats er sat til at stige til 750 kroner (ca. 107 dollars) pr. ton i 2035.

- **Afgiftens anvendelsesområde:** Afgiften gælder for udledninger fra husdyr i forhold til staldsystem, race, antal og deraf udledninger fra dyrenes fordøjelse og gødning. Landmændene får et fradrag på 60 % af afgiften, hvilket effektivt reducerer den oprindelige sats til 120 kroner pr. ton i 2030 og stiger til 300 kroner pr. ton i 2035. Indtægterne vil blive afsat til en fond, der støtter landbrugssektorens grønne omstilling. Forstyrrelse af kulstofrige jorde håndteres særskilt, hvor der pålægges en afgift pr. ton CO₂e hvis den enkelte bedrift ikke indgår i relevante udtagningsprojekter.
- **Supplerende miljøinitiativer:** Danmark planlægger at genoprette 140.000 hektar drænet tørvemose, der i øjeblikket bruges til landbrug, og etablere 250.000 hektar ny skov inden 2045. Denne indsats har til formål at øge biodiversiteten og binde kulstof, hvilket bidrager til landets miljømål. I denne sammenhæng spiller de tidligere politiske aftaler om at fordoble det økologiske landbrugsareal en vigtig rolle, da økologisk produktion i sine visioner og principper er en løsning på mere bæredygtige og klimavenlige landbrugssystemer.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Denmark is in the process of implementing the first climate tax in the world targeting agricultural emissions. The policy, scheduled to take effect in 2030, is a key element of Denmark's climate strategy and its goal of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050. Some key aspects are:

- **Implementation timeline:** The tax will be introduced in 2030, with an initial rate of 300 Danish kroner (~EUR40) per ton of CO₂ equivalent emissions. This rate is set to increase to 750 kroner (~EUR 100) per ton by 2035.
- **Scope of the tax:** The tax applies to emissions from livestock in relation to housing system, breed, number and hence emissions from animal digestion and manure spreading. Farmers involved in climate-friendly practices will receive a deduction of 60% of the tax, effectively reducing the initial rate to 120 kroner (~EUR 60) per ton in 2030 and increasing to 300 kroner per ton in 2035. The revenue will be allocated to a fund that supports the green transition of the agricultural sector. Disturbance of carbon-rich soils will be handled separately, with a tax per ton CO₂e being imposed if the individual farm is not included in relevant set-aside projects.

- **Complementary environmental initiatives:** Denmark plans to restore 140,000 ha of drained peatlands currently used for agriculture and establish 250,000 ha of new forest by 2045. These efforts aim to enhance biodiversity and sequester carbon, contributing to the country's environmental goals. In this context the previous political agreements for doubling the organic agricultural land play an important role, as organic production in its visions and principles is a solution for more sustainable and climate-friendly farming systems.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN DANISH

Implementeringen af klimaafgiften er en del af en række mål i den grønne trepartsaftale. Den grønne trepartsaftale er en aftale mellem regeringen, Landbrug & Fødevarer og Danmarks Naturfredningsforening, NNF, Dansk Metal, Dansk Industri og Kommunernes Landsforening. Aftalen blev indgået og vedtaget af Folketinget i november 2024.

Aftalen har været en proces baseret på Danmarks forpligtelse i klimaloven fra 2020 til at reducere udledningen af drivhusgasser (GHG) med 70 % inden 2030 (sammenlignet med 1990-niveauet) og opnå netto-nul inden 2050. Landbruget spiller en central rolle i denne indsats med mål om at reducere udledningen af drivhusgasser i sektoren for landbrug, skovbrug og anden arealanvendelse (AFOLU) med 55-65 % inden 2030 og at reducere kvælstofafstrømningen med 13.780 tons inden 2027 i overensstemmelse med EU's vandrammedirektiv.

Aftalen sætter følgende overordnede konkrete mål:

- Mindst 390.000 ha landbrugsjord, dvs. 15 % af det nuværende landbrugsareal, skal omlægges fra landbrug til skov, vådområder og natur.
- At 140.000 ha klimabelastende lavbundsjord (vådområder, enge og moser) omlægges til natur.
- Der skal plantes 250.000 ha ny skov, hvoraf 100.000 ha skal være urørt skov.
- At 20 % af Danmarks natur skal være fredet i 2030.
- At der indføres en CO₂-afgift på landbrugsproduktion, som træder i kraft i 2030, hvor landmændene skal betale 120 kr. pr. ton udledt CO₂, stigende til 300 kr. pr. ton udledt CO₂ i 2035. Det anslås, at aftalen har potentiale til at reducere CO₂-udledningen med mellem 1,8 og 2,6 millioner tons CO₂ i 2030.
- At det økonomiske grundlag for, at landmænd kan investere i at omstille sig til plantebaseret fødevarerproduktion, styrkes. Frem til

2030 vil der blive afsat 420 millioner kroner til Fonden for Plantebaserede Fødevarer, hvilket bringer den samlede fond op på 1,1 milliarder kroner og gør den permanent, ifølge »Den Grønne Trepert«.

Konsekvenserne for landmændene

CO₂-landbrugsafgiften vil primært være rettet mod udledninger fra husdyr, især kvæg og svin, da det er dem, der produceres mest af. Derfor skal landmændene indberette antallet af husdyr, kategoriseret efter type og produktionsformål, foderforbrug, herunder import, praksis for håndtering af gødning og brug af gødning.

Beregningen af udledningen fra den enkelte bedrift kan i høj grad baseres på oplysninger, som landmændene allerede er forpligtet til at indberette til husdyrregistret og i forbindelse med kvælstofforordningen. Dataene aggregeres derefter til den nationale drivhusgasopgørelse.

Et af de værktøjer, som landmænd kan bruge til at beregne og styre gårdens drivhusgasudledning, er ESGreen Tool, der er udviklet af SEGES Innovation. Værktøjet beregner metan, lattergas og kuldioxid. Derudover beregnes en relativ kulstofbalance, der angiver mængden af kulstof, der er lagret på landbrugsjorden. En mere detaljeret beskrivelse af dette værktøj findes i Practice Abstract #38 i denne serie.

Det forventes, at en stor del af planlægningen og implementeringen af de foreslåede ændringer i arealanvendelsen i Danmark vil blive udført af kommunerne i samarbejde med landmændenes organisationer og de kompetente civilsamfundsorganisationer. Planerne, som forventes at være færdige ved udgangen af 2025, skal dække de politiske ambitioner. En vurdering af konsekvenserne af de foreslåede ændringer i arealanvendelsen vil blive foretaget i 2026. Afhængigt af resultaterne kan der i 2027 indføres yderligere regulerende foranstaltninger, f.eks. kvoter for kvælstofudledning, for at gennemtvinge forureningsreduktioner, hvis den frivillige indsats ikke slår til. Strategien vil blive gennemgået yderligere og justeret efter behov i 2029 og hvert tredje år derefter.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

The implementation of the climate tax is part of a series of goals set in the Green Tripartite Agreement. The Green Tripartite Agreement is an agreement between the government, the Danish Agriculture & Food Council and the Danish Society for Nature Conservation, NNF, Dansk Metal, Dansk Industri and the National Association of Municipalities. The agreement was reached and adopted by the Danish Parliament in November 2024.

The agreement has been a process based on Denmark's 2020 Climate Act commitment to a 70% reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2030 (compared to 1990 levels) and achieving net zero by 2050. Agriculture plays a pivotal role in this effort, with targets to reduce GHG emissions in the Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use (AFOLU) sector by 55-65% by 2030 and to cut nitrogen runoff by 13,780 tons by 2027, in line with the EU Water Framework Directive.

The agreement sets the following overall concrete goals:

- At least 390,000 ha of agricultural land, i.e. 15% of the current agricultural area, is to be converted from agriculture to forest, wetlands and nature.
- That 140,000 ha of climate-impacting lowland soils (wetlands, meadows and bogs) are converted to nature.
- That 250,000 ha of new forest will be planted, of which 100,000 ha will be untouched forest.
- That 20% of Denmark's nature should be classified as protected areas by 2030.
- That the CO₂ tax on agricultural production is imposed, and it will come into force in 2030, where EUR16 per ton of emitted CO₂ will be paid by farmers, increasing to EUR40 per ton of emitted CO₂ in 2035. It is estimated that the agreement has the potential to reduce CO₂ emissions in the range of 1.8 million to 2.6 million tons of CO₂ in 2030.
- That the financial foundation for farmers to invest in converting to plant-based food production is strengthened. Until 2030, EUR56 million will be allocated to the Fund for Plant-based Food, bringing the total fund to EUR147 million and making it permanent, according to the "Green Tripartite".

The impact on the farmers

The CO₂ agricultural tax will primarily target emissions from livestock, particularly cattle and pigs as these are the most produced. Therefore, farmers will be required to report the number of livestock, categorized by type and production purpose; feed consumption including imports; manure management practices and fertilizer usage.

The calculation of the emissions from the individual farm can be based to a considerable extent on information that farmers are already obliged to report to the livestock register and in connection with the nitrogen regulation. The data is then aggregated into the national GHG inventory.

One of the tools that farmers can use to calculate and manage the GHG emissions of the farms is ESGreen Tool developed by SEGES Innovation. The tool calculates methane, nitrous oxide and carbon dioxide. Additionally, a relative carbon balance is calculated, indicating the amount of carbon stored on the farmland. A more detailed description of this tool is available in **Practice Abstract #38 of this series**.

It is expected that much of the planning and implementation of the proposed land use changes in Denmark will be done by municipalities in collaboration with the farmer organizations and the competent civil society organizations. The plans, that are expected to be finalized by the end of 2025, must cover the political ambitions. An assessment of the impact of these proposed land use changes will be performed in 2026. Depending on findings, additional regulatory measures, such as nitrogen emission quotas, may be introduced in 2027 to enforce pollution reductions if voluntary efforts fall short. The strategy will be further reviewed and adjusted as needed in 2029 and every three years thereafter.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

- **Economic burden on farmers:** Farmers, especially those in livestock production, will face higher expenses due to the tax. Even with the 60% deduction, costs will rise significantly by 2035. Larger, industrial farms may absorb the costs more easily, while smaller farms may struggle financially.
- **Potential shift to more intensive farming models:** in case of increased costs, farmers might intend to increase productivity per animal (e.g., higher milk yields per cow) to offset smaller herd sizes.
- **Competitiveness concerns:** Danish agricultural products may become more expensive compared to imports from countries without a similar carbon tax. If Danish farmers are forced to scale down or close, production might shift to countries with weaker climate regulations, leading to no net global reduction in emissions.
- **Potential rise in food prices:** The increased costs for farmers may be passed on to consumers, leading to higher prices for meat, dairy, and other agricultural products. This could especially affect lower-income households.
- **Lower investment for plant-based foods:** The focus on livestock farming would result in higher investment technologies from the state for bringing forward the goals of the climate agenda. Meanwhile the incentives for plant-based food gets very low.

kg of pork = 2.5 kg CO₂e; 1 kg of grain = 1 kg CO₂e; 1 kg of fruit = 0.1 kg CO₂e; 1 kg of vegetables = 0.5 kg CO₂e. (Eva Krebs – Innovationscenter for Økologisk Landbrug, 2023)

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

Den grønne trepart

URL:

<https://faktalink.dk/emner/den-gronne-trepart>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT NUMBER #42**SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE**

Ψηφιακά Αποθετήρια Γνώσης (Digital Repositories) και εργαλεία υπολογισμού άνθρακα για την Κλιματικά Ευφυή Γεωργία.

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Digital Repositories and Carbon Tools for Climate Smart Agriculture

CONTACT

Vasilis Psiroukis (vpsiroukis@aua.gr), Stathis Stathopoulos

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE – ADD KEYWORDS

1. Importance of Digital Repositories for EU agricultural sector
2. Enhanced adoption through accessible knowledge on Climate-Smart Farming and Carbon Tools

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Καθώς η γεωργία αντιμετωπίζει αυξανόμενες προκλήσεις λόγω της κλιματικής αλλαγής, η ανάγκη για λήψη αποφάσεων βάσει δεδομένων γίνεται πιο κρίσιμη από ποτέ. Οι απογραφές και βάσεις δεδομένων εργαλείων άνθρακα διαδραματίζουν βασικό ρόλο στην υιοθέτηση της Κλιματικά Ευφυούς Γεωργίας (Climate-Smart Farming - CSF), παρέχοντας δομημένες, προσβάσιμες και επιστημονικά τεκμηριωμένες πληροφορίες σχετικά με το ανθρακικό αποτύπωμα, τις εκπομπές αερίων του θερμοκηπίου (Greenhouse Gasses - GHG) και τις στρατηγικές μετριασμού. Αυτά τα εργαλεία υποστηρίζουν τους αγρότες, τους ερευνητές, τους φορείς χάραξης πολιτικής και τις αγροτικές επιχειρήσεις στην εφαρμογή βιώσιμων γεωργικών πρακτικών, τη βελτιστοποίηση της χρήσης των πόρων και τη μείωση των περιβαλλοντικών επιπτώσεων του τομέα.

Ένα από τα κύρια οφέλη των βάσεων δεδομένων εργαλείων άνθρακα είναι η ικανότητά τους να τυποποιούν και να συγκεντρώνουν πληροφορίες. Αυτές οι πλατφόρμες

συγκεντρώνουν δεδομένα για τις εκπομπές άνθρακα από διαφορετικά γεωργικά συστήματα, τύπους εδαφών, ποικιλίες καλλιεργειών και στρατηγικές διαχείρισης κτηνοτροφίας. Παρέχοντας φιλικά προς τον χρήστη περιβάλλοντα εργασίας και προσαρμόσιμα μοντέλα, επιτρέπουν στους ενδιαφερόμενους να αξιολογήσουν το ανθρακικό αποτύπωμα των γεωργικών δραστηριοτήτων, να συγκρίνουν στρατηγικές μετριασμού και να λαμβάνουν τεκμηριωμένες αποφάσεις προσαρμοσμένες στις τοπικές συνθήκες.

Επιπλέον, αυτές οι βάσεις δεδομένων υποστηρίζουν τη λήψη αποφάσεων σε επίπεδο αγροκτήματος, παρέχοντας παρακολούθηση σε πραγματικό χρόνο, προγνωστικά μοντέλα και ανάλυση σεναρίων. Οι αγρότες μπορούν να χρησιμοποιούν εργαλεία λογιστικής άνθρακα για να αξιολογούν τον αντίκτυπο των πρακτικών όπως η καλυπτική καλλιέργεια, η ακριβής λίπανση, η συντηρητική κατεργασία εδάφους και η αγροδασοπονία στην δέσμευση άνθρακα και τη μείωση των εκπομπών. Αυτά τα εργαλεία μπορούν να υποστηρίξουν τους αγρότες της ΕΕ στη βελτίωση της χωρικής ακρίβειας του ισοζυγίου άνθρακά τους και να επιτρέψουν την παρακολούθηση εκπομπών σε πραγματικό χρόνο.

Σε ένα ευρύτερο πλαίσιο, οι απογραφές εργαλείων άνθρακα μπορούν επίσης να συμβάλουν στη διαμόρφωση πολιτικών και στη δημιουργία αγορών άνθρακα. Οι κυβερνήσεις και οι ρυθμιστικοί φορείς χρησιμοποιούν αυτά τα εργαλεία (κυρίως σε περιφερειακό επίπεδο) για να παρακολουθούν την πρόοδο προς τους κλιματικούς στόχους, να σχεδιάζουν συστήματα εμπορίας άνθρακα και να επιβάλλουν πρότυπα βιωσιμότητας στη γεωργία. Παράλληλα, οι αγροτικές επιχειρήσεις και οι φορείς της εφοδιαστικής αλυσίδας μπορούν να αξιοποιήσουν τα δεδομένα άνθρακα για να εφαρμόσουν συστήματα επισήμανσης άνθρακα, να προωθήσουν τη βιώσιμη προμήθεια πρώτων υλών και να ενισχύσουν τη διαφάνεια των περιβαλλοντικών τους πρακτικών.

Συνολικά, οι απογραφές και βάσεις δεδομένων εργαλείων άνθρακα αποτελούν κρίσιμους παράγοντες για την CSF, ενισχύοντας μια κουλτούρα κοινωνικής ευθύνης, καινοτομίας και βιωσιμότητας. Παρέχοντας ακριβή και αξιοποιήσιμα δεδομένα άνθρακα, αυτά τα εργαλεία δίνουν τη δυνατότητα στον γεωργικό τομέα να προχωρήσει προς χαμηλών εκπομπών, κλιματικά ανθεκτικά συστήματα παραγωγής τροφίμων, εξασφαλίζοντας τόσο περιβαλλοντικά όσο και οικονομικά οφέλη για τις μελλοντικές γενιές.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

As agriculture faces increasing challenges from climate change, the need for data-driven decision-making has become more crucial than ever.

Carbon tool inventories and databases play a key role in enabling Climate-Smart Farming (CSF) by providing structured, accessible, and scientifically validated information on carbon footprints, GHG emissions, and mitigation strategies. These tools support farmers, researchers, policymakers, and agribusinesses in implementing sustainable practices, optimizing resource use, and reducing agriculture's environmental impact.

Carbon tool databases are key to standardize and centralize information. These platforms compile data on carbon emissions across farming systems, soil types, crop varieties, and livestock management. They help assess agricultural carbon footprints, compare mitigation strategies, and support data-backed decisions suited to local conditions.

These inventories also aid farm-level decisions through real-time monitoring, predictive modeling, and scenario analysis. Farmers can evaluate the impact of practices on carbon sequestration and GHG reduction. Such tools enhance spatial accuracy and enable tracking of emissions in real time.

On a broader scale, carbon tools support policy development and market incentives. Governments use them—mainly at regional levels—to track climate goals, design carbon credit systems, and enforce sustainability standards. Agribusinesses use carbon data for labeling, sustainable sourcing, and transparency.

Ultimately, carbon inventories are key enablers of CSF, fostering accountability, innovation, and sustainability. These tools empower agriculture to shift toward low-emission, climate-resilient food systems, delivering both environmental and economic benefits. CFD has undertaken to compile such a list of existing tools in Europe. This database is available on the CFD website and will be available during 2025 on the 'Farming for Climate' platform.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

As agriculture faces increasing challenges from climate change, the need for data-driven decision-making has become more crucial than ever. Carbon tool inventories and databases play a key role in enabling Climate-Smart Farming (CSF) by providing structured, accessible, and scientifically validated information on carbon footprints, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and mitigation strategies. These tools support farmers, researchers, policymakers, and agribusinesses in implementing sustainable

agricultural practices, optimizing resource use, and reducing the sector's environmental impact.

One of the main benefits of carbon tools databases is their ability to standardize and centralize information. These platforms compile data on carbon emissions across different farming systems, soil types, crop varieties, and livestock management strategies. By offering user-friendly interfaces and customizable models, they allow stakeholders to assess the carbon footprint of agricultural operations, compare mitigation strategies, and make data-backed decisions tailored to local conditions.

Furthermore, these inventories support farm-level decision-making by offering real-time monitoring, predictive modeling, and scenario analysis. Farmers can use carbon accounting tools to evaluate the impact of cover cropping, precision fertilization, conservation tillage, and agroforestry on carbon sequestration and emission reduction. These tools can ultimately support EU farmers to enhance spatial accuracy of their carbon balance and enable real-time tracking of emissions.

From a broader perspective, carbon tools inventories can potentially also contribute to policy development and market incentives. Governments and regulatory bodies use these tools (primarily on regional levels) to track progress toward climate commitments, design carbon credit systems, and enforce sustainability standards in agriculture. Additionally, agribusinesses and supply chain actors can leverage carbon data to implement carbon labeling schemes, promote sustainable sourcing, and enhance their environmental transparency.

Ultimately, carbon inventories and databases serve as critical enablers of CSF, fostering a culture of accountability, innovation, and sustainability. By equipping stakeholders with accurate and actionable carbon data, these tools empower the agricultural sector to transition toward low-emission, climate-resilient food production systems, ensuring both environmental and economic benefits for future generations.

CFD has undertaken to compile such a list of existing tools in Europe. This database is available on the CFD website and will be available during 2025 on the 'Farming for Climate' platform.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #43**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

Storytelling for Impact – A Narrative-Based Communication Approach in Climate Farm Demo

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

N/A

CONTACT

Isidora Čolić (isidora.colic@biosense.rs)

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Stronger stakeholder engagement through relatable and structured storytelling
2. Improved communication of climate-smart farming outcomes across all CFD actors
3. Enhanced uptake of innovations via accessible, audience-tailored narratives

THEMATIC AREA

N/A

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

In the Climate Farm Demo, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) play an important role in communicating climate-smart farming practices. To support this, a storytelling-based approach has been developed to turn complex research and data into compelling, relatable stories that resonate with farmers, advisors, policymakers, and the public.

This method helps present real-life impacts of climate-smart practices, making the benefits more accessible and engaging. The approach is structured around three main components:

Step 1: Identify Relevant Information (See Message Box)

Use the Message Box to define key elements of your story:

- **Audience** – Who are you trying to reach?
- **Problem** – What challenge are they facing?
- **So what?** – Why does this matter to them?
- **Solution** – What climate-smart practice or innovation helps?
- **Benefit** – What difference does this solution make?

Step 2: Build the Narrative (4-Step Story Structure)

Craft a powerful story using these elements:

- **Setting** – What is the current situation or knowledge level?
- **Characters** –
 - *Villain*: e.g., climate change, extreme weather
 - *Victim*: e.g., the farmer or ecosystem under threat
 - *Hero*: e.g., a climate-smart solution like no-till or cover cropping
- **Plot** – Describe how the villain affects the victim using real evidence.
- **Moral** – Show how the solution (hero) helps and share a clear takeaway.

Step 3: Structure the Story for Engagement

Organize your story to maximize impact:

- **Section 1:** Introduce the problem and the characters
- **Section 2:** Share who, where, when, and the solution
- **Section 3:** Provide background and key evidence
- **Section 4:** Conclude with how the issue is solved and what action is needed

This storytelling method has been integrated into DEC training and support materials within CFD to strengthen demonstration events and farmer engagement. Stories make technical solutions personal and memorable helping inspire real change on farms across Europe.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

Effective communication is critical for the success of the Climate Farm Demo (CFD) project. It ensures that climate-smart farming practices, results and outcomes are accessible and compelling to all relevant stakeholders. To support this goal, CFD has introduced a narrative-based storytelling

approach to enhance how project partners, including farmers and advisors, communicate project findings and results.

This storytelling method provides a structured way to translate technical knowledge, field experiences, and scientific results into narratives that resonate with diverse audiences, including farmers, advisors, policymakers, industry representatives, and the general public. By doing so, it strengthens dissemination, knowledge exchange, and stakeholder engagement across the CFD network.

Why Use Storytelling?

Storytelling helps make complex information more accessible and memorable. Climate-smart farming practices often involve technical terms, long-term impacts, and systemic changes. Presenting them through real-world stories increases understanding and relevance, while fostering emotional connection and motivation to act.

The storytelling approach supports:

- Improved engagement at demonstration events and workshops
- Greater learning retention through relatable examples
- Stronger alignment between science and practice
- Enhanced dissemination of project outcomes to a wider audience

Step 1: Identifying Relevant Information Using the Message Box

The Message Box is a communication tool that helps structure key messages clearly. It supports project actors in identifying:

- **Audience** – Who needs to hear this (e.g., farmers, advisors, policymakers)?
- **Problem** – What challenge does the audience face?
- **So what?** – Why does this issue matter to them?
- **Solution** – What practice, innovation, or result addresses the challenge?
- **Benefit** – What is the value or positive outcome for the audience?

This structure ensures that stories are grounded in real concerns and demonstrate clear value.

Step 2: Building the Narrative Using a Four-Element Framework

A compelling narrative is more than a set of facts. It involves characters, tension, resolution, and a clear message. This approach uses four key components:

- **Setting** – The current situation and assumptions of the audience
- **Characters** – Identifying the:
 - *Villain* (e.g., climate stress, soil degradation)
 - *Victim* (e.g., farmers, land, biodiversity)
 - *Hero* (e.g., a climate-smart solution, research insight, or practice)
- **Plot** – The problem as experienced by the victim, supported by data or testimonials
- **Moral** – The conclusion, highlighting how the solution (hero) creates positive change

Step 3: Structuring the Story for Dissemination

Stories developed using this approach can be used across multiple communication formats:

- Field stories and articles
- Practice Abstracts
- Video scripts
- Policy briefs
- Social media posts
- Reports and presentations

The story is structured into:

- **Section 1: Introduction** – Present the problem and the key actors
- **Section 2: Description** – Detail the situation, location, and solution
- **Section 3: Context and Evidence** – Present the background and supporting findings
- **Section 4: Resolution** – Highlight outcomes, key lessons, and a call to action

Inserting quotes from farmers or advisors helps humanise the message and increases trust in the story.

Relevance Across the Climate Farm Demo Network

This approach can be used by all project actors in any project to communicate their results effectively. Whether for scientific dissemination, public outreach, or policy influence, narrative-based storytelling strengthens impact and ensures that messages reach and resonate with the right audiences.

This method also supports the core aims of CFD:

- Encouraging adoption of climate-smart practices

- Fostering peer learning and advisor engagement
- Supporting transparent and inclusive communication
- Linking local experiences with European-level impact

Conclusion

Narrative-based storytelling offers a practical and powerful tool for disseminating Climate Farm Demo outcomes. By combining scientific rigour with personal experience, this approach helps build bridges between knowledge holders and knowledge users. As climate-smart farming becomes increasingly important, the ability to communicate clearly, credibly, and meaningfully is essential.

By adopting this storytelling method, project partners not only increase visibility of their results but also support a culture of engagement, innovation, and sustainability within European agriculture.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: Message box - a communication tool that helps structure key messages clearly

This is only an example targeting general public, with hypothetical issue

PRACTICE ABSTRACT NUMBER #46**SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE**

Verringerung der Ammoniakemissionen durch Optimierung der Futterrationen von Milchkühen

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Reducing Ammonia Emissions by Optimizing the Feed Rations of Dairy cows

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Luxembourg, Continental Europe

CONTACT

Rocco Lioy (rocco.lioy@convis.lu)

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Ammonia emissions
2. Optimization of protein content in ration
3. Protein autonomy

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

Dairy cattle

THEMATIC AREA

Herd management

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Die Optimierung der Rohproteinaufnahme bei Milchkühen (siehe Abbildung 3, Maßnahme 16 in der CFD-AMM-Bibliothek) ist ein wichtiger Hebel zur Verringerung der Ammoniak- und Treibhausgasemissionen.

Im Rahmen des Projektes AUTOPROT (www.autoprot.eu) wurde festgestellt, dass ein beträchtlicher Teil des Proteins, das im Betrieb erzeugt und verfüttert wird, von der Milchviehherde nicht verwertet wird. Dieses nicht verwertete Eiweiß ist von großer Bedeutung, denn es erhöht die Gefahr von Ammoniakverlusten. Im Projekt AUTOPROT wurde ferner gezeigt, dass Betriebe mit einem hohen Selbstversorgungsgrad an Eiweiß (Eiweißautarkie) einen niedrigeren Anteil an nicht-verwerteten Eiweiß aufweisen. Man kann rechnerisch darstellen, dass das nicht verwertete Eiweiß dem Luxuskonsum an Eiweiß durch das Milchvieh entspricht.

Aus der Literatur ist bekannt, dass hohe Rohproteingehalte in der Ration von Rindern im Allgemeinen zu einer erhöhten Ausscheidung des Stickstoffs unter Form von Harn führen. Dabei ist gerade der Harn dafür verantwortlich, dass Ammoniak entweicht, da der Harnstoff als Hauptbestandteil des Harns sehr schnell in Ammoniak umgewandelt wird. Wenn das Rohprotein in den Rationen gut am Bedarf der Tiere angepasst ist, scheiden die Tiere den Stickstoff vermehrt über Kot aus, der deutlich weniger zu den Ammoniakemissionen beiträgt.

Dank einer Studie von Sajeev et al. (2017) wurde weiter bekannt, dass im Rindviehbereich das Reduzierungspotential der Ammoniakverluste durch Verringerung um 1% des Rohproteinüberschusses in der Ration bei 17% des Gesamtausstoßes liegt.

Ein wesentlicher Punkt ist die Definition einer Zielgröße für die Rationsoptimierung. Nach Ansicht von Experten lassen sich Rohproteingehalte in der Ration von Milchkühen bis auf ein Niveau von 15% in der Trockensubstanz ohne Einbußen in der Milchleistung absenken. Für das Jungvieh ist nach Ansicht der Experten ein Rohproteingehalt in der Ration von 14% ausreichend. Aus diesen Überlegungen konnte für die CONVIS-Betriebe ein Einsparungspotential an NH₃-emissionen über die Rationsoptimierung von rund 10 kg Stickstoff pro ha. Von diesen Einsparungen stammen 90% allein aus der Rationsoptimierung der Milchkühe.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

The practice of optimizing crude protein intake in dairy cows (See Figure 3, Measure 16 in CFD AMM library) is a key lever for reducing both ammonia and GHG emissions.

As part of the AUTOPROT project (www.autoprot.eu), it was established that a considerable proportion of the protein produced and fed on the farm is not utilised by the dairy herd. This unutilised protein is of great importance because it increases the risk of ammonia losses. The AUTOPROT project also showed that farms with a high degree of self-sufficiency in protein (protein self-sufficiency) have a lower proportion of unutilised protein. It can be shown mathematically that the unutilised protein corresponds to the luxury consumption of protein by the dairy cattle.

It is known from the literature that high crude protein levels in cattle rations generally lead to increased excretion of nitrogen in the form of urine. It is the urine that is responsible for the escape of ammonia, as urea, the main component of urine, is very quickly converted into ammonia. If the crude protein in the rations is well adapted to the animals' requirements, the animals excrete more nitrogen via faeces, which contributes significantly less to ammonia emissions.

Thanks to a study by Sajeev et al. (2017), it also became known that the potential for reducing ammonia losses in cattle by reducing by 1% the crude protein surplus in the ratio is 17% of the total output.

A key point is the definition of a target value for ration optimisation. According to experts, crude protein levels in the rations of dairy cows can be reduced to a level of 15% in dry matter without any loss in milk yield. In the opinion of the experts, a crude protein content of 14% in the ration is sufficient for young cattle. Based on these considerations, the CONVIS farms in the AUTOPROT project were able to achieve potential savings in NH₃ emissions of around 10 kg of nitrogen per ha through ration optimisation. Of these savings, 90% came from ration optimisation for dairy cows alone.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Im Rahmen des Projektes AUTOPROT (www.autoprot.eu) wurde festgestellt, dass ein beträchtlicher Teil des Proteins, das im Betrieb erzeugt und verfüttert wird, von der Milchviehherde nicht verwertet wird. Dieses nicht verwertete Eiweiß ist von großer Bedeutung, denn es erhöht die Gefahr von Ammoniakverlusten. Im Projekt AUTOPROT wurde ferner gezeigt, dass Betriebe mit einem hohen Selbstversorgungsgrad an Eiweiß (Eiweißautarkie) einen niedrigeren Anteil an nicht-verwerteten Eiweiß

aufweisen. Die Eiweißautarkie kann in Funktion der Futtevorlage bzw. des Bedarfs an Eiweiß der Milchviehherde ausgedrückt werden (Abb.1).

Das nicht verwertete Eiweiß ist auf engstem mit dem Rohproteinüberschuss in der Ration bzw. mit dem Luxuskonsum vom Milchvieh verbunden. Man kann nämlich rechnerisch zeigen, dass der Unterschied zwischen aufgenommenem Eiweiß, und dem von den Tieren als Milch und Fleisch verwertete Eiweiß umso größer ist, je höher die Menge an Eiweiß ist, das über dem Bedarf hinaus vom Milchvieh aufgenommen wird. Dann steigen auch die ausgeschiedenen Stickstoffmengen und damit das Ammoniak-Ausstoßpotential (Abb.2).

Aus der Literatur ist bekannt, dass hohe Rohproteingehalte in der Ration von Rindern im Allgemeinen zu einer erhöhten Ausscheidung des Stickstoffs unter Form von Harn führen. Dabei ist gerade der Harn dafür verantwortlich, dass Ammoniak entweicht, da der Harnstoff als Hauptbestandteil des Harns sehr schnell in Ammoniak umgewandelt wird. Wenn das Rohprotein in den Rationen gut am Bedarf der Tiere angepasst ist, scheiden die Tiere den Stickstoff vermehrt über Kot aus, der deutlich weniger zu den Ammoniakemissionen beiträgt.

Für die CONVIS-Betriebe wurde im Rahmen des Projektes ein durchschnittlicher Rohproteingehalt bei den Milchkühen von 16,7% in der Trockensubstanz festgestellt. Beim Jungvieh lag der Mittlere Rohproteingehalt bei 14,5% in der Trockensubstanz.

Dank einer Studie von Sajeev et al. (2017) wurde weiter bekannt, dass im Rindviehbereich das Reduzierungspotential der Ammoniakverluste durch Verringerung um 1% des Rohproteingehaltes in der Ration bei 17% des Gesamtausstoßes liegt.

Ein wesentlicher Punkt ist die Definition einer Zielgröße für die Rationsoptimierung. Nach Ansicht von Experten lassen sich Rohproteingehalte in der Ration von Milchkühen bis auf ein Niveau von 15% in der Trockensubstanz ohne Einbußen in der Milchleistung absenken. Für das Jungvieh ist nach Ansicht der Experten ein Rohproteingehalt in der Ration von 14% ausreichend. Aus diesen Überlegungen konnte für die CONVIS-Betriebe im AUTOPROT-Projekt ein Einsparungspotential an NH₃-emissionen über die Rationsoptimierung von rund 10 kg Stickstoff pro ha. Von diesen Einsparungen stammen 90% allein aus der Rationsoptimierung der Milchkühe.

Wir halten fest

- Im Rahmen des Projektes AUTOPROT wurde der Zusammenhang zwischen Rohprotein-Überschuss in der Ration vom Milchvieh und den Ammoniakverlusten untersucht.
- Die im Rahmen des Projektes AUTOPROT untersuchten CONVIS-Betriebe weisen einen Rohproteingehalt in der Ration der Milchkühe von 16,7% auf.
- Vom Rohprotein-Gehalt kommt man zu den Ammoniak einsparungen durch die Annahme, dass die Reduzierung von 1% des Rohprotein-Gehaltes eine Verringerung der Emissionen um 17% bewirkt.
- Über die Rationsoptimierung von Milchkühen (Absenkung des Rohproteingehaltes auf 15%) und Jungvieh besteht ein Verringerungspotential von bis 25% der NH₃-Verluste. Im Fall der CONVIS-Betriebe macht dies rund 10 kg NH₃-N/ha.
- Allgemein gilt: Eine hohe Selbstversorgung mit Eiweiß (hohe Eiweißautarkie) ist eine wesentliche Voraussetzung dafür, niedrige Ammoniakemissionen zu erreichen.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

As part of the AUTOPROT project (www.autoprot.eu), it was established that a considerable proportion of the protein produced and fed on the farm is not valorized by the dairy herd. This not valorized protein is of great importance because it increases the risk of ammonia losses. The AUTOPROT project also showed that farms with a high degree of self-sufficiency in protein (protein self-sufficiency) have a lower proportion of non-valorized protein. Protein self-sufficiency can be expressed as a function of the feed supply or the protein requirement of the dairy herd (Fig. 1).

The not valorized protein is closely linked to the crude protein surplus in the ration or to the luxury consumption of dairy cattle. It can be shown mathematically that the higher the amount of protein consumed by dairy cattle more than their requirements, the greater the difference between the protein consumed and the protein valorized by the animals as milk and meat. This also increases the amount of nitrogen excreted and thus the potential for ammonia emissions (Fig. 2).

It is known from the literature that high crude protein levels in cattle rations generally lead to increased excretion of nitrogen in the form of urine. It is the urine that is responsible for the escape of ammonia, as urea, the main component of urine, is very quickly converted into ammonia. If the crude protein in the rations is well adapted to the animals' requirements, the

animals excrete more nitrogen via faeces, which contributes significantly less to ammonia emissions.

As part of the project, an average crude protein content of 16.7% in the dry matter of dairy cows was determined for the CONVIS farms. For young cattle, the average crude protein content was 14.5% in dry matter.

Thanks to a study by Sajeev et al. (2017), it also became known that the potential for reducing ammonia losses in cattle by reducing the crude protein content in the ration by 1% is 17% of the total output.

A key point is the definition of a target value for ration optimization. According to experts, crude protein levels in the rations of dairy cows can be reduced to a level of 15% in dry matter without any loss in milk yield. In the opinion of the experts, a crude protein content of 14% in the ration is sufficient for young cattle. Based on these considerations, the CONVIS farms in the AUTOPROT project were able to achieve potential savings in NH₃ emissions of around 10 kg of nitrogen per ha through ration optimization. Of these savings, 90% came from ration optimization for dairy cows alone.

Main conclusions

- As part of the AUTOPROT project, the relationship between excess crude protein in the ration of dairy cattle and ammonia losses was analysed.
- The CONVIS farms analysed showed a crude protein content of 16.7% in the ration of the dairy cows.
- From the crude protein content, the ammonia savings are derived by assuming that reducing the crude protein content by 1% results in a 17% reduction in emissions.
- By optimizing the rations of dairy cows (lowering the crude protein content to 15%) and young cattle, there is potential to reduce NH₃ losses by up to 25%. In the case of the CONVIS farms, this amounts to around 10 kg NH₃_N/ha.
- In general, a high protein autonomy (high protein self-sufficiency) is an essential prerequisite for achieving low ammonia emissions.

PHOTOS

Figure 1: Calculation of protein autonomy for dairy farms

Figure 2: Relation between protein autonomy and nitrogen losses

Measure ID	Measure	Level	Category	Sub-category	Key practice suitable for organic farms?	Organic and Halal/MSA	Key adaptation levels: compatible or not/low	Statistical evidence provided	Reference for climate mitigation effect and N2O	Priority of climate mitigation effect
1	Improve feed by re-evaluation assets	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed	Organic	M		3	Correlation between milk yield and N2O	3
1	Optimize daily ration of forage	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	A	3/through	1	kg of forage stock for storage losses	1
3	Creating an "addition" and evaluate assets	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	A	3/through	1	Are available for additional grazing	1
4	Feed responses and choice for cattle	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	A	3/through	1	Optimal choice for cattle (milk)	1
5	Optimizing feedstock growing management	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	A		1	Time of sowing between cattle	1
6	Feedstock growing	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	A		1	Are available for early grazing	1
7	Optimizing woolly breeds selection	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	AM		1	Proportion of woolly breeds in diet	1
8	Stocking on pasture (see ref.)	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	AM		1	Proportion of milk	1
9	Continuous full grazing (see animal or per area)	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	M		1	Use of hay or full grazing	1
10	Feeding of horses (see 1.10.1 and 1.10.2)	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	M		1	Use of hay	1
11	Feeding of herbivores (see 1.10.1 and 1.10.2)	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	M		1	Herbivores: without feed (kg)	1
12	Use of forage in feed	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	M		1	Proportion of forage in diet	1
13	Use of forage with partial feed	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	M		1	Use of forage in diet	1
14	Use of forage in feed	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	M		1	kg of forage in diet	1
15	Optimization of forage content in feed	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	M		1	Proportion of forage content in the diet	1
16	Optimization of forage content in feed	Animal	Animal husbandry and feeding	Feed Dairy	Organic	M		1	Proportion of forage content in the diet	1

Figure 3: Measure 16 from the Climate Farm Demo Mitigation Adaptation Library

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

Technical handbook to calculate protein autonomy in dairy farms, in German (also French version available)

URL:

https://www.autoprot.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Livable-2.1_Technisches-Handbuch.pdf

Title/Description

Technical report about the mitigation potential of ammonia emissions via optimization of ration of dairy cows, in German (also French version available)

URL:

https://www.autoprot.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/20220719_8.2._DE.pdf

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #48**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

Reinforcing Your Key Message During Demonstration Events with the use of Props

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

N/A

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Effective demonstration events
2. Use of props
3. Higher retention rates

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

N/A

THEMATIC AREA

N/A

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

When organizing a demonstration event, you want your key message to come across clearly and stick with the participants. A powerful tool to reinforce your key message is the use of props. The word “prop” is borrowed from the theater and movie industry, where it refers to a “movable article or

object used on the set of a movie or play.” Furthermore, it is also defined as “a support to keep something from shaking or falling.” Building on these definitions, in demonstration events, we refer to a “prop” as “an object that supports or emphasizes the key message during a demonstration.”

Props can take many forms, such as information boards, soil samples, feed samples, a harvester, or even a cow. The main idea is that they are simple and enhance understanding of the key message at a glance. For example, when you want to stress the importance of making quality silage to reduce feed costs, a bale of silage can be presented alongside a meal. Or, when explaining different plots on a farm, participants can be provided with a simple map of the plots and their characteristics.

By using a prop, the learning retention rate of participants can be doubled to 20%, compared to a simple lecture, which has a retention rate of 10%. But, if you want to significantly increase the retention rate to 75%, you can introduce a prop that participants can actively engage with. For example, if you want to discuss the difference between multiple varieties of forage, you can present different samples that participants can feel, smell, taste, etc., along with a description of their characteristics. Or, when discussing the quality of a clover field, a clover scorecard can be handed out to the participants to help them judge the clover content in a grass/clover sward.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

More tips on organizing effective demo events can be found in the demo design guide (<https://zenodo.org/records/13939148>) and in the FarmDemo Training Kit (<https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/>)

PHOTOS

Picture 1: a bale of silage can be presented alongside a meal during a demo event in Ireland

Source: John Greaney, Teagasc

Picture 2: Map of an agroforestry system of a Dutch farm

Source: Willem Hendriks, ZLTO

Picture 3: Different varieties of forages and their characteristics

Source: Elena Bortolazzo, CRPA

Picture 4: Clover scorecard used during demo events in Ireland

Source: Michael Egan, Teagasc

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)**Title/Description**

ClimateFarmDemo- Demo Design Guide for On-farm Demonstrations

URL:

<https://zenodo.org/records/13939148>

Title/Description

FarmDemo Training Kit

URL:

<https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #52**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

Effective Communication for Demo Events - Boosting Reach, Engagement, and Impact

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

N/A

CONTACT

Isidora Čolić (isidora.colic@biosense.rs)

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Targeted outreach and higher attendance
2. Wider visibility and knowledge transfer
3. Stronger networks and lasting impact

THEMATIC AREA

N/A

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Announcing and promoting your farm demonstration events is key to ensuring strong participation, meaningful exchange, and lasting impact. Whether you are a farmer or advisor, good communication helps bring the right people to your event, builds interest, and ensures your experiences reach others who can benefit from them. Sharing your event before and after also supports the wider goals of the Climate Farm Demo project by spreading knowledge on climate-smart farming practices.

Announcing your demo event

A clear and timely announcement helps participants plan and signals that their presence is valued. Tailor your message and use tools that match your audience:

- **Direct messages** (email, SMS, phone calls) to specific farmers or advisors.
- **Local channels** farmers trust—WhatsApp groups, bulletin boards, newsletters, Facebook groups.
- **Networks and institutions** (advisors, farming groups, local authorities).

Include the **date, time, location, topic, and key benefits** of attending. Explain what will be demonstrated or learned in a practical way.

Promoting your demo

Promotion builds curiosity and widens your audience:

- Share posts via **social media channels** (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn).
- Tag partners and Climate Farm Demo to extend reach.
- Use **engaging visuals**-photos of your farm or previous events.
- Highlight the benefit: e.g. "See how cover crops reduce fertiliser needs."

After the event

Follow up with a **thank-you message** and a **summary post**:

- Share **main outcomes** and **good photos**.
- Mention who attended and what was learned.
- Tag key participants or supporters.

Benefits of good communication:

- Stronger turnout and engagement
- Wider knowledge sharing
- More impact from your effort
- Better visibility for your farm or organisation

By planning your event communication before and after, you help ensure it makes a difference for both your local community and farmers across Europe.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

Promoting and announcing your farm demonstration events is essential for ensuring a successful turnout, meaningful exchange, and long-term impact. Whether you are a farmer or advisor, good communication helps bring the right people to your event, creates interest in the topic, and allows others to benefit from your experience. Sharing your event before and after also supports the wider goals of your project by spreading knowledge on climate-smart farming practices.

Announcing your demo event

The first step is a clear and timely announcement. This helps potential participants plan and signals that their presence is welcome and valued. Depending on your audience, you can use different tools:

- **Direct invitations:** Personal emails, text messages, or calls work well—especially when tailored to the interests of specific farmers or advisors.
- **Farmer-used communication channels:** Post in local WhatsApp or Facebook groups, cooperatives' newsletters, or bulletin boards at local supply stores.
- **Advisor networks and local institutions:** Inform advisory services, local government or extension services so they can help share the news.

Your announcement should include the **date, time, location, topic, and key benefits** of attending. Keep it clear and practically explain what participants can expect to see or learn.

Promoting your event

Promotion adds visibility and builds curiosity beyond your direct contacts. Consider:

- **Posting on your farm or advisory organisation's social media** (Facebook, Twitter/X, Instagram, LinkedIn).
- **Tagging project** (e.g., Climate Farm Demo), local institutions or cooperatives to extend reach.
- **Using engaging visuals:** Share photos from past events or a picture of the host farm to attract attention.
- **Mentioning why the event matters**—for example, “See how cover crops help reduce fertiliser costs.”

After the event

Your work doesn't end when the event does. Sharing a **thank-you message** shows appreciation and builds relationships for future events. A short

follow-up post with key takeaways and a few good photos helps spread the knowledge further and increases impact:

- Post highlights from the demo day on social media. (good photos or videos are highly recommended)
- Mention who attended, what was discussed, and what was learned.
- Use quotes or feedback from participants if available.
- Tag participants, partners, and any supporting organisations.

Key benefits for farmers and advisors:

- Stronger participation and engagement
- Wider sharing of knowledge and practical solutions
- Stronger local networks and visibility for your work
- Greater impact from your demo effort

By announcing, promoting, and following up on your event, you help ensure your demo farm's experience contributes to the wider adoption of climate-smart farming practices—both locally and across Europe.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #63**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

Farmers with Power - A 6-Step Approach to Sustainable Energy Management in Climate Farming

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Belgium, temperate maritime climate

CONTACT

Marleen Gysen (marleen.gysen@boerenbond.be)

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

- Reduced energy costs through smart monitoring and optimisation
- Increased use of renewable energy and on-farm production
- Improved energy efficiency and climate resilience in farming operations

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

All

THEMATIC AREA/SECTOR

Energy management

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

With rising energy costs and the need for climate-smart farming, farmers require structured guidance to improve energy efficiency. The Belgian farmers' organisation Boerenbond has developed a practical manual to

help advisors and farmers navigate this transition. The *Farmers with Power!* tool offer a six-step approach to optimising energy use, reducing costs, and fostering a greener, climate-smart agricultural sector.

1. Know your farm

Advisors work with farmers to analyse energy consumption: how much is needed, when, and at what power level. This may involve assessing energy use across different seasons and peak operational times. Energy monitoring systems can help track usage and identify areas for improvement.

2. Energy bill optimisation

Farmers should review their energy bills for potential savings, such as negotiating better rates or adjusting contracts to better align with usage patterns.

3. Energy-saving measures

Reducing energy use can involve upgrading lighting, optimising heating, ventilation, and cooling (HVAC) systems, and investing in efficient machinery and equipment.

4. Renewable energy production

Farmers can install solar panels, wind turbines, or biomass systems to cut fossil fuel reliance and emissions. Feasibility depends on space, local climate conditions, labour, and financial resources.

5. Smart use of own produced energy

Aligning energy use with production periods, shifting energy-intensive tasks, and investing in storage solutions maximises renewable energy benefits.

6. Collaboration on energy

Farmers can join energy communities to share costs, access funding, and negotiate better energy deals. Cooperatives can also implement energy-efficient infrastructure and demand-side management strategies, enhancing energy resilience.

This tool supports farmers, advisors, and energy consultants in advancing energy efficiency and sustainability in climate-smart farming.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

This tool is part of the ClimateSmartAdvisors toolbox and is not yet online.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #64**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

The Use of LED Lighting in Dairy Housing to Increase Performance and Lower Costs and Carbon Footprint

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

United Kingdom, temperate climate

CONTACT

Richard Lloyd (richardl@i4agri.org)

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Improved Milk Production
2. Lower Electricity Costs
3. Improved Animal Welfare

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

Indoor Dairy Housing

THEMATIC AREA

Herd Management

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Providing better lighting in dairy setups can increase yields by 10%. Milking cows exposed to light levels over 150 lux for 16 hours a day can increase yields by 8–13%, as increased daylight reduces the cows' melatonin levels. This, in turn, enables more of their naturally occurring milk-producing hormones to be secreted. However, it is also important to provide 8 hours of darkness to

optimise the cows' circadian rhythm, which improves health and reproductive performance.

Farmers must take care when measuring light. It is important to take measurements at cow level, ideally with sensors that automatically activate the lighting systems. A common mistake is placing lights only above the feed passage and not distributing them evenly throughout the cubicle building. A cow typically spends only 3–4 hours per day at the feed barrier but rests in a cubicle for 12–16+ hours per day. If lighting is inadequate in the cubicles, where the cow spends most of her time, she will not be exposed to the required photoperiod.

Red night lights may be used to facilitate cow movement and observation during darkness. The intensity of red light has minimal or no effect on the cows' perception of darkness and thus does not significantly impact melatonin secretion. There should be no brighter lights in any part of the barn, and cows need 2–4 weeks on average to adjust.

LED lights with blue-enriched white light (400–500 nm) are an ideal light source and help reduce energy costs. These can also be incorporated into units that provide red night lights. Optimising the light spectrum and photoperiod helps regulate the cows' circadian rhythm by mimicking summer daylight conditions, which stimulates feed intake and milk production. Red night lights also improve fertility and general well-being, while providing a better environment for farm workers and aiding in heat detection.

Ideal LED lighting: more yield, better welfare, more profit, lower costs, and a reduced carbon footprint.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

At the recent Climate Farm Demo project meeting in Slovenia, the herd management thematic visit highlighted the importance of having suitable lighting in cow sheds, especially when dairy cows are housed for extended periods.

In the UK, and elsewhere, it is common for transparent roofing panels to be used to allow light into cow sheds during the day. However, the transparency of these panels deteriorates as dirt accumulates and the materials degrade, so it is common to encounter sheds with substandard light levels.

Providing better lighting in dairy setups can increase yields by up to 10%. Milking cows exposed to light levels over 150 lux for 16 hours a day can see yields increase by 8–13%, as the extended daylight reduces melatonin levels in cows, which in turn enables more of their naturally occurring milk-producing hormones—IGF-1 and prolactin—to be secreted. However, it is also important to provide 8 hours of darkness to optimise the cows' circadian rhythm. This promotes better sleep patterns and reduces stress, thus improving health and reproductive performance.

Farmers must take care when measuring light. Measurements should ideally be taken with sensors at cow level that automatically activate the lighting system. A common mistake is placing lights only above the feed passage and not evenly throughout the cubicle building. Cows typically spend just 3–4 hours per day at the feed barrier, while resting in cubicles for 12–16+ hours daily. If lighting is inadequate in the cubicles, cows will not receive the required photo period.

Red night lights can be used to facilitate cow movement and observation during darkness. The intensity of red light has minimal or no effect on cows' perception of darkness and thus does not significantly affect melatonin secretion. There should be no brighter lights in any part of the barn. Cows need, on average, 2–4 weeks to adjust to new lighting.

There has been much research in humans on the role that light—and blue light in particular—plays in Seasonal Affective Disorder (SAD). Symptoms of SAD include fatigue, sleep disturbances, and changes in appetite. Cows are no different.

In dairy housing, LED lights are commonly used due to their lower energy consumption and longer lifespan compared to other light sources. The light spectrum of LEDs can vary significantly depending on the type used.

LED lights with blue-enriched white light (400–500 nm) are ideal and help reduce energy costs. These can be integrated into units that also provide red night lights. Optimising the light spectrum and photoperiod helps regulate cows' circadian rhythms by mimicking summer daylight conditions, which increases levels of IGF-1 and prolactin, stimulates feed intake, and boosts milk production. Red night lights also support fertility, general well-being, better working environments for farm staff, and heat detection.

The impact on carbon footprint—measured per litre of milk—can be significant. Increased milk production, improved feed efficiency, and

reduced energy costs per litre are estimated to deliver a 4% reduction in CO₂e per litre.

This impact could be even greater in farms with very poor housing conditions, as the estimate does not account for expected improvements in fertility, cow health, or reduced replacement rates.

Ideal LED lighting: more yield, better welfare, more profit, lower costs, and a reduced carbon footprint.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: LED lights in daylight, cow sheds

Photo 2: Red night lights in cow shed

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #65**SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE**

Inventário de projetos, iniciativas e decisores políticos

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Inventory of Projects, Flagship Initiatives, and Policymakers for the Climate Farm Demo (CFD) Network

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Portugal, Mediterranean zone

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Collaboration
2. Synergies
3. Knowledge exchange

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S)

O desenvolvimento de colaborações com entidades externas ao projeto ClimateFarmDemo tem três objetivos principais:

- 1) Integrar o conhecimento e a investigação de outros projetos, iniciativas e decisores políticos,
- 2) Dar visibilidade ao projeto e divulgar os seus recursos e principais resultados;
- 3) Criar oportunidades de cooperação.

Para facilitar este tipo de colaboração, o projeto estabeleceu uma lista de projetos, iniciativas e decisores políticos relevantes, através da contribuição de vários parceiros do consórcio.

O Inventário de Projetos, Iniciativas e Decisores Políticos (PIP) do Climate Farm Demo (CFD) é uma ferramenta estratégica fundamental para estabelecer a cooperação a nível europeu e nacional entre o Climate Farm Demo e outros PIPs. Esta ferramenta lista vários projetos, iniciativas e decisores políticos que podem ser relevantes para os parceiros do CFD.

Ao utilizar esta base de dados, os parceiros do CFD podem encontrar novas oportunidades de colaboração, tanto a nível nacional como a nível europeu. Tais oportunidades serão, por exemplo, a organização de conferências e workshops conjuntos, a integração de metodologias e ferramentas de outros projetos no trabalho desenvolvido no Climate Farm Demo e até a troca de conhecimento para dar feedback aos decisores políticos.

Foram recolhidos contributos de todos os parceiros do projeto, bem como desenvolvida uma pesquisa orientada para os decisores políticos relevantes da Comissão Europeia, do Parlamento Europeu e do Conselho Europeu. Posteriormente, foi desenvolvida uma pesquisa e análise detalhadas para recolher informações relevantes sobre os projetos, bem como sobre iniciativas e decisores políticos.

A base de dados resultante permite um mapeamento detalhado com descrição dos PIPs e a relevância para os diferentes parceiros do Projeto. Esta ferramenta foi o primeiro passo para o estabelecimento de sinergias que poderão ter valor acrescentado para o Climate Farm Demo.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Establishing links with external networks has three main goals:

1. Integrate knowledge and research from other projects, initiatives and policymakers,
2. Give visibility to the project and disseminate its resources and main outputs.
3. Create opportunities for cooperation.

To facilitate this type of collaboration, the project has established a list of relevant Projects, Initiatives and Policymakers with contributions of several partners in the consortium.

The Inventory of Projects, Flagship Initiatives, and Policymakers (PIP) of the Climate Farm Demo (CFD) is a key strategic tool for establishing cooperation

at European and national levels between Climate Farm Demo and other PIPs. This tool lists various projects, initiatives and policymakers that might prove to be relevant for partners in CFD.

By using this database, CFD partners may find new opportunities for collaboration both at national and at European level. Such opportunities might include the organization of joint conferences and workshops, integrating methodologies and tools from other projects into the work developed in Climate Farm Demo and even knowledge exchange with policymakers to provide feedback on current policy measures.

Input was collected from all project partners, as well as a targeted search for relevant policymakers within the EU Commission, EU Parliament and EU Council. Afterwards, a detailed search and analysis was made to collect relevant information of the identified past, ongoing, and future projects, as well as flagship initiatives and policymakers. The resulting database enables a detailed mapping of PIP names, description and relevance to different partners in the Project. This tool was the first step towards establishing synergies that have an added value for Climate Farm Demo.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #69**SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE**

La lisiothermie, une pratique pour réduire les consommations d'énergie et les émissions de GES au bâtiment pour les élevages porcins en système lisier.

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Manure Cooling, a Practice for Reducing Energy Consumption and GHG Emissions of Pig Buildings with Slurry Systems

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

France, temperate climate

CONTACT

Annie Soulier (annie.soulier@ifip.asso.fr)

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE – ADD KEYWORDS

1. Less GHG emissions
2. Less ammonia emission
3. Reducing energy consumption

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

Pig housing on slatted floors

THEMATIC AREA/SECTOR

Pigs sector

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

La France, comme l'Union Européenne, se fixe d'atteindre la neutralité carbone à l'horizon 2050, avec des réductions des émissions de gaz à effet de serre applicables à tous les secteurs d'activités. L'élevage porcin représente 6% des émissions de GES liées à l'élevage en France. Pour les élevages en système lisier, les émissions de GES liées aux effluents sont dominées par le méthane. L'ammoniac est indirectement impliqué car elle contribue à la formation de protoxyde d'azote, autre GES fortement impactant sur le réchauffement climatique.

La lisiothermie est une technique basée sur la récupération des calories des lisiers stockés en porcherie. Un liquide caloporteur circule dans un réseau de tubulures installé en fond de préfosse permettant l'échange calorique avec le lisier. Il permet d'acheminer les calories vers une pompe à chaleur reliée à un ballon d'eau chaude ou à un système de chauffage pour préchauffer l'air de maternité par exemple. Si l'objectif initial de cette technique est la réduction de la consommation d'énergie, elle peut aussi contribuer à réduire l'impact environnemental des porcheries avec, d'après des essais français conduits par l'Ifip, un abattement de 20% sur l'ammoniac et de 60% sur le méthane. Néanmoins, cette technique est plutôt à réserver aux nouveaux bâtiments ; le réseau de tubulures devant être inséré dans la dalle béton de la préfosse ; son installation en bâtiments existants conduisant à une réduction notable du volume de stockage des lisiers en bâtiment.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

France, like the European Union, aims to achieve carbon neutrality in 2050 by reducing greenhouse gas emission in all sectors. Pig farming accounts for 6% of livestock-related greenhouse gas emissions in France. For pig farms with slurry systems, GHG emissions linked to effluents are dominated by methane. Ammonia is indirectly involved because of its contribution to the formation of nitrous oxide, another greenhouse gas with a major impact on global warming.

Manure cooling is a technique based on recovering heat from slurry stored in pig farms. A heat-transfer fluid circulates through a network of pipes installed at the bottom of the pre-pit, allowing heat exchange with the slurry. This system transfers the recovered heat to a heat pump connected to a hot water tank or a heating system, for example, to preheat the air in farrowing units. While the primary goal of this technique is to reduce energy

consumption, it can also help reduce the environmental impact of pig farms, with French trials conducted by Ifip showing a 20% reduction in ammonia emissions and a 60% reduction in methane emissions. However, this technique is better suited to new buildings, as the pipe network must be embedded in the concrete slab of the pre-pit; installing it in existing buildings would significantly reduce the available storage volume of slurry within the facility.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Depending on the practice used, reducing GHG emissions from buildings also involves thinking about outdoor storage methods as part of an overall approach to avoid shifting emission sources.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: Manure cooling at the bottom of the pre-pit

Photo credit: IFIP

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

Etude de l'influence du refroidissement du lisier sur les émissions gazeuses de NH₃, N₂O et CH₄ de porcs à l'engraisement

Guingand N, Rousselière Y, Lagadec S. and Hassouna Melinda, 2025. 57ème Journées de la Recherche Porcine en France, 57, 107-112.

URL:

<https://www.journees-recherche-porcine.com/>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #70**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

How to Structure an Effective European Project with a Wide Range of Agricultural Actors in Several Countries

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

All

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. European project running efficiently
2. National ecosystems are connected, locally and with the European level
3. Advisors are trained with the best practices across Europe to support farmers in their climate transition.

PRODUCTION SYSTEM (IF RELEVANT)

All

THEMATIC AREA

All

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

If you're leading a project that involves diverse actors (i.e. farmers, advisors, cooperatives, researchers, and agro-industries) across multiple countries,

like the European "Climate Farm Demo" (CFD), structuring your project effectively is key to success. Here are some insights from over two years of CFD experience:

1. Clear Role Definition

In large-scale projects such as CFD which involves over 80 partners, 1,500 farmers, 250 advisors, and National Coordinators across 26 countries, defining roles is crucial. Clearly identify the levels of responsibility and differentiate between those who carry out tasks (field actors) and decision-makers who provide resources. The goal is to keep the organization simple, flexible, and efficient, with dedicated channels to address each actor type.

2. Linking European and National/Local Levels

To ensure the network functions well across countries, the following steps are key:

- **Leverage Existing Networks:** Build on national or regional demo-farm networks, advisory groups, or cooperatives. If none exist, help partners create one.
- **National Coordinators:** Appoint someone to lead local efforts, connect with national stakeholders and act as an interface with the European level (see dedicated Practice Abstract).
- **Common Operating Framework:** Create a flexible, cohesive framework for national networks to follow.
- **Regular Engagement:** Organize recurring missions like annual national meetings to keep stakeholders engaged.
- **Quarterly Coordination:** Connect all National Coordinators regularly through a dedicated management group and online meetings to share updates, challenges, and solutions.
- **Involving Advisors and Experts:** Advisors are crucial for guiding farmers through climate-smart practices. Ensure that National Coordinators facilitate these networks, connect with advisors' managers for support, and involve experts to train advisors on new practices and facilitation skills.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

Are you a project leader and want to set up a network gathering many different actors, such as farmers, advisors, researchers, cooperatives, suppliers and agro-industries in over 25 countries, as is the case for the European "Climate Farm Demo" (CFD) project?

After more than 2 years up and running, here are some initial observations based on CFD's experience on how to run a project that works. Our first and

most important outcome is to structure the project organisation with defined roles and link the European level with the national and local levels.

Identify roles

In a very large-scale project such as CFD, over 80 partners are involved in the management and activities, while there are 1,500 farmers, over 250 advisors, and 30 work packages and task leaders, 20 thematic and sectors specialists and 26 National Coordinators (i.e. 1 per country involved in demonstration events in the field).

One of the critical points in the running of such a project is to clearly identify the levels of responsibility and decision-making and to differentiate between those who carry out tasks (field actors) and decision-makers who provide resources. Each actor must understand their role in the global framework, while the organization remains simple and flexible.

The challenge is to develop channels through which these actors can be addressed effectively. In CFD, we organise bi-annual meetings (1 face-to-face and 1 online) and targeted webinars for decision-makers, while structuring a specific operating model for field actors (see below).

Articulate the European level with each national network

It is vital that the network is connected at national and local levels: how to do so?

1. Ideally, establish the national network by building on existing national or local demo-farm networks derived from previous projects, cooperative, agroindustry or advisor groups: this ensures the network is already operational. If no such network exists, the project must support the national partners for its creation. This requires attention and organisational flexibility, as well as the support of operational intermediaries (see next point);
2. Appoint National Coordinators: its role is to create links with the partners involved in its own country, lead local actors towards a common goal and act as an interface with the European level (please see dedicated Practice Abstract "*The key role of the National Coordinator in a project such as CFD: scope and limits of his tasks*");
3. Define a common operating framework for these national networks that is sufficiently solid and coherent, while remaining flexible and 'comfortable';
4. Provide resources in the country language – or translate them if necessary: tools, trainings and documentation will be most useful to advisors and farmers if available in their own language;

5. Define recurring missions and key actions for national networks, such as committing them to organising a national meeting each year;
6. Connect the National Coordinators together through a quarterly online meeting: they will share their highlights, needs and issues, while you can communicate information relevant for all national networks. One of the keys to success is to create an operational intermediate management function through a 'Network Management Unit', which is extremely important and valuable in making the project run smoothly;
7. Connect with the network of advisors in each country, building on current networks whenever possible. Indeed, advisors are crucial to support farmers in the journey towards climate smart transition;
8. Appoint the National Coordinator as Climate Farm Advisors' network facilitator, responsible for creating the dynamics and synergies needed to disseminate climate smart farming practices as widely as possible;
9. Engage with the advisors' direct managers to ensure they will provide the means for the advisors to act in the field;
10. Involve thematic experts to train the advisors on new climate smart practices but also on facilitating skills (see dedicated *Practice Abstract mentioned above*).

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Assess the feasibility and conditions for implementing Climate-Smart Farming Practices in the various countries involved in the project

A key element of a project of the scale of CFD is to carry out an inventory of the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) in the different countries and to anticipate the different situations in which they operate. For a 'Coordination and Support Actions' (CSA) project like CFD, the key point is the link between the advisors and the type of advisory network that exists in the different countries. In fact, in CFD, the widespread dissemination of Climate Smart Practices relies on advisors who are competent both in climate change mitigation and adaptation issues, and in facilitating on-farm demonstration events. The project must be able to provide support solutions (from initial training to ongoing skills upgrading).

In addition, one of the conditions of feasibility is the question of how to support the project partners, first and foremost the volunteer farmers involved in the project. They commit time and energy to organising demonstration events and taking part in cross-fertilisation activities. The question is how to compensate them financially for the time they invest. But

there is also the challenge of financing the mitigation or adaptation measures to be implemented. In CFD, these two points are not covered by the project, which means that 'mirror financing' solutions have to be found where necessary. The key success factor here, as in the CFD project, is to dedicate resources to structuring synergies between projects, initiatives and policymakers.

Do not underestimate the language barrier

The language barrier appears at all levels and for all roles in a European project on the scale of CFD. But it is particularly sensitive and can become a major limiting factor at the key level of advisors, but also of farmers.

At advisor level, the language barrier may prove to be a critical point, mainly in terms of 1/ getting to know and using the tools for assessing the capacity of farms to adapt to and mitigate climate change; 2/ helping them to develop their technical skills on the issues of adapting to climate change and mitigating the effects of agricultural practices on it.

At farmer level, the language barrier is a major obstacle to exchanges and cross-learning between peers from different countries. There is a risk that some of the operational knowledge produced cannot be disseminated widely if it is not translated.

A key success factor is to anticipate the need for translation and to dedicate project resources to the implementation of tools (based in particular on the fast-growing field of Generative Artificial Intelligence) that can overcome the language barrier.

Do not underestimate the effort required to deploy tools for assessing the capacity of farms to adapt to and mitigate climate change.

One of the first lessons to be learnt from the CFD project is to recognise the difficulties and resources that need to be mobilised to deploy tools in the field with advisors and farmers. These difficulties can be seen at a number of overlapping levels: 1/ the choice of tools; 2/ the skills required to use these tools; 3/ the technical skills required to deal with 'climate' issues; 4/ the skills required to organise and facilitate high-quality demonstration events on farms; 5/ the skills required for communication and dissemination activities; 6/ the motivation of agricultural professionals and the political priorities given to climate issues.

The choice of tools is particularly complex and requires a compromise approach for all situations requiring the adaptation of tools designed for different farming systems and soil and climate conditions. Indeed, the long

development times for the tools required for these adaptations cannot always be included in the project.

The level of political priority given to climate issues can have major consequences, particularly in terms of all the measures to support farmers in implementing new, more virtuous practices, sharing the management of climate risks, etc.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: CFD Country-Level Network

CFD EUROPEAN-LEVEL NETWORK

Photo 2: CFD European-Level Network

EUROPEAN-LEVEL NETWORK

Photo 3: European-Level Network

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #71**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

The Impact of Slurry Separation on Nutrient Content of the Separated Fractions

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

United Kingdom, NW Europe maritime climate

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Creation of organic material with contrasting dry matter and nutrient contents
2. Allows for a more targeted application of organic materials
3. Applicable to all slurry and digestate based systems

PRODUCTION SYSTEM (IF RELEVANT)

Livestock/Biogas

THEMATIC AREA

Manure storage and spreading

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Slurry separation is the mechanical division of livestock slurry or digestate, to create a liquid and solid fraction.

Three common methods of separation used on farm include:

1. Screw press
2. Roller screen press
3. Decanting centrifuge

The efficiency of the separator to remove dry matter (DM) into the solid fraction underpins the association of nutrients into the relevant fractions. Typically, the liquid fraction is characterised by low DM, high readily available nitrogen (N) and low phosphorus (P) and carbon content. The solid fraction has a higher DM, and P content, and has been acknowledged for its potential benefits to improve soil quality indicators such as water holding capacity, aggregate stability and drainage. Typical UK values for separated organic materials are presented in the AHDB Nutrient Management Guide (RB209).

The partitioning of P into the solid fraction can benefit the farmer in supporting the potential use of separated solids to maintain or build up soil P levels without over-applying N, and the potential for P-rich solids to be removed from an area with excess soil P.

Ultimately, farmers are faced with a trade-off between the cost and availability of separation methods. Centrifuge separators are reportedly the most effective at creating a phosphate (PO_4^-) rich solid material. However, this technique is the most expensive per tonne of separated material, has the highest electricity demand, is the most expensive to install, and has a lower throughput of slurry compared to a screw press. It is for farmers to assess which technology is best suited for their slurry management based on their business and regulatory requirements.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

The information for this Practice Abstract was generated as part of the UK Government Defra-funded project (Defra RDE372 – Evaluating the agronomic and environmental impacts of slurry and digestate separation).

PHOTOS

Fraction	Material	DM	TN	TP	TK
		%	kg/t fresh weight (FW)		
Solid	Cattle slurry	20	4.0	2.0	3.3
	Pig slurry	20	5.0	3.7	2.0
	Farm digestate	24	5.6	4.7	6.0
Liquid	Cattle slurry	4	3.0	1.2	2.8
	Pig slurry	3	3.6	1.1	2
	Farm digestate	3	1.9	0.6	2.5

Table 1: Typical UK values for separated organic materials

Source: AHDB Nutrient Management Guide (RB209)

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #72

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

The Key Role of the National Coordinator in a Project such as CFD: Scope and Limits of His/Her Tasks

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

European scale

CONTACT

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BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. European CSA project
2. Intermediate management

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

The Climate Farm Demo (CFD) project promotes Climate Smart Farming Practices across 26 countries, involving 1,500 farmers and 250+ advisors. To ensure effective implementation, the project relies on National Coordinators (NCs), who serve as the crucial link between the European management team and national agricultural networks.

The NC's main responsibilities include:

- Facilitating smooth communication between the European team and national stakeholders.
- Reporting challenges and progress from their country to the project management team.
- Ensuring all project documents are accessible in the local language.
- Managing the national network by organizing knowledge exchange events and maintaining advisor and farmer engagement.

- Supporting and monitoring national partners in carrying out their expected tasks.
- Expanding the project's reach by engaging policymakers, researchers, and farmers through effective communication.
- Contributing to policy development by working with national and regional authorities.

NCs may have expertise in specific agricultural fields, but they are not required to be specialists in all aspects of climate adaptation and mitigation. However, their role has certain limitations:

- They do not have decision-making authority over national partners.
- They cannot provide specialized training outside their expertise.
- If solely acting as NCs, they are not directly responsible for audits, adaptation plans, or demonstration events.

Overall, NCs play a vital role in ensuring the project's success by bridging communication gaps, supporting local stakeholders, and broadening the impact of climate-smart farming initiatives.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

Climate Farm Demo (CFD) is a project that focuses on the deployment of Climate Smart Farming Practices by those working in the field, in this case farmers engaged in various production systems, accompanied by advisors. The CFD project is deploying its scheme in 26 countries and with 1,500 farmers, accompanied by more than 250 advisors. To bring such a programme to life, it is essential to rely on an intermediary operational management link, the 'National Coordinator' (NC). The NC is essential, because he is familiar with the operating methods (the 'codes') of his country's agricultural ecosystem and, of course, carries out his tasks in the local language!

The NCs are the " pivotal " links between the project's management at global (European) level and the networks deployed in each of the countries (26 countries in the case of CFD). Their main roles are to:

- Ensure a fluid exchange between the team managing the project at European level and the deployment of national actions on the field (and make sure that all the documents made available within the project are accessible in a language that everyone in their country understands),
- Act as a link between the partners in its country (mainly advisory bodies and farmers) while managing the national network by

organizing skill-building and knowledge exchange events and ensuring continued engagement among advisors and farmers,

- Contribute (under the responsibility of the project's general management) to monitoring and supporting the tasks expected of the partners in his/her country throughout the project,
- Broaden the impact of the Climate Farm Demo project within his country by engaging a broader audience, including the farming and scientific communities, through suitable communication channels. Build relationships with national and regional policymakers and contribute to shaping the strategic plan for Policy Initiatives and Policies (PIPs),
- Report on initiatives and difficulties encountered by advisors and farmers in his/her country to the project management.

The NC may of course combine several roles and be an advisor, or a scientific specialist in a particular field or sector, or even be involved in running a Living Lab. However, they are not required to be scientific specialists in all areas of climate change adaptation or mitigation.

The main limitations of his mission are as follows:

- They have no decision-making responsibility in relation to the partners in their country involved in the project.
- They are unable to provide training to their country's advisors or farmers in specialized subjects, except in their own areas of expertise.
- In case they perform only the role of the NC, they are not directly involved in delivering project outputs such as audits, adaptation and mitigation plans, or demonstration events.

From CFD's experience, it is essential to connect the National Coordinators together in order to create a dynamic peer's network. We experienced an efficient pattern through a quarterly online meeting when NCs share highlights, needs and issues of their national networks, while coordination team can communicate information relevant for all national networks.

One of the keys to success is to create an operational intermediate management function through a 'Network Management Unit', which is extremely important and valuable in making the project run smoothly.

In CFD, during the first two years we created small groups of 5 to 7 NCs to create favourable conditions for the NCs to get to know each other. From the third year, once the working links had been developed, we moved to groups of 8 to 10 NCs to widen the circle of exchanges, which has proved to be quite effective and relevant.

In addition, the NCs systematically have a dedicated face-to-face session at the annual meetings organised in one of the partner countries.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #73

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

The Role of Soils for Climate Mitigation and Adaptation

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

All EU

CONTACT

Lin Bautze (lin.bautze@fibl.org) and Markus Steffens

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Improved soil fertility and long-term productivity
2. Enhanced climate resilience and carbon sequestration
3. Reduced GHG emissions through sustainable soil management

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

Arable crops, horticulture, market gardening, protein and oil seed crops, viticulture

THEMATIC AREA

- Soil health and biodiversity
- Grassland management, forage production, crops management, agroforestry and relation to landscape

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Why Soils Matter

Arable soils are the foundation of farming across the EU, crucial for fertility, productivity, profitability, and long-term sustainability. Soils are now central to climate debates due to their role in reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and supporting resilient agriculture. Scientists are developing methods to quantify soil organic carbon (SOC) for climate mitigation, while policymakers explore carbon credit schemes. Farmers are increasingly interested in carbon farming as a potential income source.

Effects of Climate Change on Soils

Climate change poses challenges to soil health, including:

- Increased erosion and nutrient leaching from heavy rainfall and extreme weather
- Frequent waterlogging or droughts, impacting plant productivity
- Greater pest pressure and altered microbial activity due to temperature changes
- Faster decomposition of soil organic matter under warmer conditions
- Negative impacts on soil structure and stability

Investing in soil health is essential to preserve ecosystems and maintain productivity.

How to Build Healthy and Fertile Soils

Building healthy soil takes time. Long-term studies, like Switzerland's DOK trial, show that biodynamic and organic practices can sequester more SOC than conventional systems. Farmers can apply two strategies to stabilize or increase carbon in soils: (a) increase carbon inputs (e.g., cover crops, compost) and/or (b) reduce carbon losses (e.g., reduced tillage, rewetting peatlands).

Soil and Climate Goals

While SOC is often seen as a solution to the climate crisis, challenges remain—measuring, verifying, ensuring additionality, permanence, and addressing leakage and sequestration potential. SOC is not a simple fix, but carbon farming can increase farmer engagement and foster sustainable practices.

Balancing climate goals with other sustainability aspects supports the long-term health and fertility of soils.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

Why Soils Matter

The foundation of most farms across the EU is their arable soils, along with their fertility and health. These factors regulate not only soil functions but also productivity, financial returns, and the long-term sustainability of production. In fact, 95% of the world's food is either directly or indirectly produced on soils (1).

In recent years, arable soils have become an increasingly important focus in the climate debate. Their role in reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and supporting resilient agriculture across the EU is a topic of significant discussion. Scientists are working to develop methods that can accurately quantify soil organic carbon (SOC) to assess its potential as a climate mitigation solution. Policymakers are striving to integrate these findings into carbon credit schemes, while farmers are becoming increasingly interested in carbon farming as a potential source of income.

Effects of Climate Change on Soil Health, Fertility, and Carbon

The unavoidable effects of climate change will present new and additional challenges for farmers related to their soils:

- Erosion and nutrient leaching are likely to increase due to more intense and frequent rainfall, winds, and extreme weather events.
- Waterlogging or changing soil moisture caused by flooding or droughts will become more frequent, posing challenges to plant productivity.
- Increased pest and disease pressures due to changing temperature patterns.
- Higher rates of soil organic matter decomposition driven by warmer temperatures.
- Negative impacts on soil structure and stability (2).

Therefore, investing now in healthy and fertile soils is essential for farmers to preserve the ecosystem functions of arable soils and maintain crop productivity in the long term.

What Can Be Done to Build Healthy and Fertile Soils

Building healthy, fertile, and resilient soils takes time (3). Long-term experiments, such as the DOK trial in Switzerland, show that it takes many years to see the effects of certain management practices on SOC. These studies have demonstrated that biodynamic and organic farming practices

may have greater potential to sequester SOC compared to conventional systems. Organic fertilizers, such as compost, farmyard manure, and cover crop systems, have been proven beneficial in stabilizing or increasing SOC (4). In general, farmers can focus on two approaches:

- Increasing carbon inputs (e.g., through cover crops, compost, organic manure, etc.)
- Reducing carbon losses (e.g., through reduced tillage, rewetting of peatlands, and similar practices) (5).

By adopting these methods, farmers can contribute to building and maintaining healthy, fertile soils over the long term.

Soils and Climate Goals

Currently, there are high expectations that SOC will provide a solution to the climate problem. However, scientific evidence indicates that relying on SOC as a definitive solution for achieving a climate-neutral Europe presents significant challenges. These include issues related to the measurement, verification, and reporting of SOC. Concerns arise from differences in soil carbon sequestration potential, additionality, permanence, and leakage effects (6).

As a result, expectations for soils as an easy fix for climate challenges need to be tempered. Nonetheless, carbon farming can serve as a starting point for advisory efforts and for farmers to engage with the topic of climate change. It can encourage constructive dialogue about potential adaptations to management practices that align with climate mitigation, adaptation, and broader sustainability goals.

It is crucial to emphasize: holistic solutions are needed ones that balance climate goals with other sustainability objectives, ensuring long-term soil fertility and the health of arable soils.

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Description/Title

EEA Europe (2015): Soil and climate change. Infographic.

URL

<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/soil-and-climate-change>

Description/Title

The state of soils in Europe – Fully evidenced, spatially organised assessment of the pressures driving soil degradation

European Commission: European Environment Agency, Joint Research Centre, Arias-Navarro, C., Baritz, R. and Jones, A., Arias-Navarro, C.(editor), Baritz, R.(editor) and Jones, A.(editor), Publications Office of the European Union, 2024

URL

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/7007291>

Description/Title

Soil and climate. Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick.

Paul Mäder; Markus Steffens; Maïke Krauss; Andreas Fliessbach; Hans-Martin Krause; Colin Skinner; Martina Lori; Giulia Bongiorno; Matthias Klais; Christine Arncken; Hansueli Dierauer; Else Bünemann; Adrian Müller; Urs Niggli; Andreas Gattinger (2022).

URL

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Description/Title

The DOK trial: a 45 years comparative study of organic and conventional cropping systems. Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick.

Andreas Fliessbach, Hans-Martin Krause (both FiBL Switzerland), Klaus Jarosch, Jochen Mayer (both Agroscope), Astrid Oberson (ETH Zürich), Paul Mäder (FiBL Switzerland) (2024).

URL

<https://www.fibl.org/en/shop-en/1741-dok-dossier-en>

Description/Title

Agricultural limitations to soil carbon sequestration: Plant growth, microbial activity, and carbon stabilization, Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment

Tuomas J. Mattila, Noora Vihanto, Volume 367, 2024, 108986, ISSN 0167-8809,

URL

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2024.108986>.

Description/Title

Carbon farming: Are soil carbon certificates a suitable tool for climate change mitigation?

Carsten Paul, Bartosz Bartkowski, Cenk Dönmez, Axel Don, Stefanie Mayer, Markus Steffens, Sebastian Weigl, Martin Wiesmeier, André Wolf, Katharina Helming, Journal of Environmental Management, Volume 330, 2023, 117142, ISSN 0301-4797

URL

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.117142>.

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #88**SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE**

La valutazione dell'impatto ambientale negli allevamenti

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Environmental Impact Assessment in Livestock Farming

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

Italy and all Europe

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Carbon footprint
2. Environmental sustainability
3. Life Cycle Assessment

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

Livestock farming

THEMATIC AREA

Herd management

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

L'allevamento degli animali è un importante componente della filiera agroalimentare e dell'economia rurale; tuttavia è stato messo in evidenza che questo è uno tra i principali emettitori di gas ad effetto serra (GHG),

principalmente metano (CH₄), il protossido di azoto (N₂O) e l'anidride carbonica (CO₂). La valutazione della quantità di questi gas prodotti negli allevamenti può essere fatta attraverso l'applicazione della metodologia del Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) che è un metodo, standardizzato dalle norme ISO 14040 e 14044, che permette di calcolare gli impatti ambientali di un prodotto o di un servizio lungo tutto il suo ciclo di vita. L'LCA si compone di diverse fasi: la definizione dello scopo/obiettivo dell'analisi; la scelta dell'unità funzionale che è associata alla produzione di emissioni GHG (kg FPCM o kg LWG) e del confine del sistema; l'analisi d'inventario attraverso cui si fa la raccolta dei dati necessari per l'analisi; la scelta dei fattori di emissione con cui si andranno a calcolare tutti i gas prodotti in allevamento. Una volta individuati questi fattori di emissione si procede al calcolo del contributo di metano, protossido di azoto e anidride carbonica al riscaldamento globale che viene espresso in base al loro Global Warming Potential (misura del contributo di ogni gas serra al riscaldamento globale) che è riferito ad 1 kg di CO₂ equivalente ed è pari a 28 kg di CO₂ equivalente per il CH₄ e a 265 kg di CO₂ equivalente per il N₂O.

L'LCA applicata al settore agricolo e zootecnico permette di valutare la sostenibilità ambientale degli allevamenti, focalizzandosi sulle cause dei principali impatti, permettendo al contempo di valutare e attuare ipotesi di miglioramento, in modo da migliorare la performance ambientale di ciascuna azienda. Con l'applicazione di questa metodologia, si possono identificare i processi a più alta intensità di emissione e di uso delle risorse all'interno del processo produttivo e, successivamente, individuare le opzioni di miglioramento più adeguate.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Livestock production is an important component of the agri-food chain and the rural economy; however, it has been identified as one of the main emitters of greenhouse gases (GHG), primarily methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The assessment of these gases in livestock farming can be conducted using the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, a standardized method under ISO 14040 and 14044 that calculates the environmental impacts of a product or service throughout its life cycle.

LCA consists of several phases:

- Defining the purpose/objective of the analysis

- Choosing the functional unit associated with GHG emissions (kg Fat and Protein Corrected Milk (FPCM) or kg live weight gain (LWG) and setting system boundaries
- Conducting inventory analysis to collect necessary data
- Selecting emission factors to calculate all gases produced on the farm

Once emission factors are identified, the contributions of methane, nitrous oxide, and carbon dioxide to global warming are calculated using their Global Warming Potential (GWP)—a measure of each gas's impact relative to CO₂ equivalent (CO₂-eq). The values are 28 kg CO₂-eq for CH₄ and 265 kg CO₂-eq for N₂O and 1 kg CO₂ eq for CO₂. (See *IPCC: Fifth Assessment Report*)

Applying LCA to agriculture and livestock enables an assessment of environmental sustainability, identifying the main impact sources while also evaluating and implementing potential improvements. This methodology helps pinpoint high-emission and resource-intensive processes within production systems, allowing for the identification of optimal improvement strategies to enhance environmental performance.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

L'allevamento degli animali è un importante componente della filiera agroalimentare e dell'economia rurale; tuttavia è stato messo in evidenza che questo è uno tra i principali emettitori di gas ad effetto serra (GHG), principalmente metano (CH₄) che deriva dalla fermentazione della sostanza organica nel rumine e nelle deiezioni; il protossido di azoto (N₂O) che si forma per reazioni a carico dei composti azotati escreti dall'animale, nei depositi degli effluenti e in campo e dalle reazioni dei fertilizzanti azotati di sintesi; e l'anidride carbonica (CO₂) che deriva dalla combustione dei carburanti fossili utilizzati nelle lavorazioni colturali e dalla produzione degli alimenti acquistati, dei fertilizzanti e dei pesticidi.

La valutazione della quantità di questi gas prodotti negli allevamenti può essere fatta attraverso il calcolo di indicatori specifici (Carbon Footprint). Il Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) è un metodo, standardizzato dalle norme ISO 14040 e 14044, che permette di calcolare gli impatti ambientali di un prodotto o di un servizio lungo tutto il suo ciclo di vita attraverso il calcolo di specifici indicatori che si compone di diverse fasi: la definizione dello scopo/obiettivo dell'analisi (per esempio la comparazione di diversi sistemi produttivi); la scelta dell'unità funzionale che è associata alla produzione di emissioni GHG (kg FPCM o kg

LWG) e del confine del sistema che generalmente è il *farm gate*; l'analisi d'inventario attraverso cui si fa la raccolta dei dati necessari per l'analisi; la scelta dei fattori di emissione con cui si andranno a calcolare tutti i gas prodotti in allevamento. In accordo con quanto riportato nelle linee guida dell'IPCC, questa scelta può essere fatta applicando tre livelli di precisione il Tier 1: approccio semplificato basato sull'utilizzo di valori di default, il Tier 2: può essere utilizzato se ci sono dati specifici per quella fonte emissiva; il Tier 3: è un approccio fortemente specifico perché considera dei fattori relativi ai sistemi produttivi del paese interessato dall'analisi. Una volta individuati questi fattori di emissione si procede al calcolo del contributo di metano, protossido di azoto e anidride carbonica al riscaldamento globale che viene espresso in base al loro Global Warming Potential (misura del contributo di ogni gas serra al riscaldamento globale) che è riferito ad 1 kg di CO₂ equivalente ed è pari a 28 kg di CO₂ equivalente per il CH₄ e a 265 kg di CO₂ equivalente per il N₂O.

L'LCA applicata al settore agricolo e zootecnico permette di valutare la sostenibilità ambientale degli allevamenti, focalizzandosi sulle cause dei principali impatti, permettendo al contempo di valutare e attuare ipotesi di miglioramento, in modo da migliorare la performance ambientale di ciascuna azienda. Con l'applicazione di questa metodologia, si possono identificare i processi a più alta intensità di emissione e di uso delle risorse all'interno del processo produttivo e, successivamente, individuare le opzioni di miglioramento più adeguate. La metodologia LCA può essere applicata non solo alle aziende agricole, ma anche all'industria alimentare, e più in generale a tutta la filiera agroalimentare, in modo da valutare la sostenibilità ambientale dei prodotti e delle aziende. In tal modo ciascuna azienda potrà conoscere gli aspetti ambientali critici della propria filiera produttiva e valutare opportunità di miglioramento. L'LCA è alla base di sistemi e strumenti a supporto della gestione ambientale quali ad esempio etichette e dichiarazioni ambientali di prodotto.

LONGER DESCRIPTION - IN ENGLISH

Livestock production is an important component of the agri-food chain and the rural economy; however, it has been highlighted as one of the main sectors emitting greenhouse gases (GHG). These include methane (CH₄), which derives from the fermentation of organic matter in the rumen and manure; nitrous oxide (N₂O), which is formed through reactions involving nitrogen compounds excreted by animals during manure storage and in the field, as well as from the reactions of synthetic nitrogen fertilizers; and carbon dioxide (CO₂), which comes from the combustion of fossil fuels used in crop processing and from the production of purchased feed, fertilizers, and pesticides.

The assessment of GHG emissions in livestock farming can be conducted through the calculation of specific indicators, such as the Carbon Footprint. The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a standardized method under ISO 14040 and 14044 that calculates the environmental impacts of a product or service throughout its life cycle by analyzing specific indicators. The LCA process consists of several phases:

- Defining the objective of the analysis (e.g., comparing different production systems).
- Selecting the functional unit associated with GHG emissions (kg Fat and Protein Corrected Milk (FPCM) for dairy production or kg live weight gain (LWG) for beef production) and determining the system boundaries, generally the farm gate.
- Conducting an inventory analysis, collecting necessary data.
- Choosing emission factors to calculate all GHG emissions from the farm.

According to IPCC guidelines, emission factors are classified into three levels of precision:

- Tier 1: A simplified approach using default emission factors, not country specific.
- Tier 2: Used when a key source category is highly relevant, incorporating country-specific production characteristics and more detailed influencing factors.
- Tier 3: A highly specific approach that requires extensive experimental data related to the specific production system of the country.

Once emission factors are identified, the contributions of methane, nitrous oxide, and carbon dioxide to global warming are calculated using their Global Warming Potential (GWP). This expresses emissions in CO₂-equivalents, where CH₄ = 28 kg CO₂-eq and N₂O = 265 kg CO₂-eq per 1 kg emitted.

The LCA methodology, when applied to agriculture and livestock, enables an assessment of environmental sustainability, identifying major impact sources while also allowing for the evaluation and implementation of improvement strategies to enhance environmental performance.

By applying LCA, the highest-emission processes and resource-intensive activities within production systems can be identified, leading to the most appropriate improvement measures. This methodology can be used not only for agricultural farms but also in the food industry and, more broadly, across

the entire agri-food chain to assess the environmental sustainability of products and farms.

With this approach, farms can identify critical environmental aspects of their production systems and evaluate opportunities for improvement. LCA also serves as the foundation for environmental management tools, including eco-labels and environmental product declarations.

PHOTOS

Figure 1: System boundaries in a dairy farm.

Figure 2: Structure of a Life Cycle Analysis evaluation.

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Title/Description

IPCC: Fifth Assessment Report

URL:

[Fifth Assessment Report — IPCC](#)

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 91

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

Advisors Supporting Farmers in Climate Action

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

EU

CONTACT

Tom O'Dwyer (tom.odwyer@teagasc.ie)

3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Farmer Engagement: Higher adoption of mitigation and adaptation practices.
2. Advisor-Farmer Connection: Strengthened relationships and trust.
3. Advisor Benefits: Increased job satisfaction and professional fulfillment.

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

All production systems.

THEMATIC AREA

Not applicable

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

The Climate Farm Demo Top Tips for advisors supporting farmers in the uptake of climate mitigation and adaptation measures are listed below:

1. **Get to know the farmers you are trying to influence.** A range of factors, such as age, access to finance and attitude towards risk,

impact the willingness of farmers to change their farming practices. Don't forget the personal touch – make the connection with the farmer, and their family. And most importantly, listen to the farmer's arguments, fears and wishes.

2. **Highlight the positives** including good practices and the progress made by the farmer, without being afraid of calling out the areas for improvement.
3. **Keep it simple.** Farmers need to know that the recommended solutions are backed up by science, that the new approaches work to reduce GHG emissions...but don't necessarily need to know all the scientific details.
4. **Frame your messages carefully**, highlighting the benefits to the farmer (profitability, productivity, work-life balance) of adopting climate mitigation or adaptation measures. Farmers tend to implement climate-beneficial measures due to other farm-related benefits.
5. **Always prepare before meeting with the farmer.** Use available benchmarking tools/ GHG assessment tools to understand the farm's current GHG emissions profile. Review other available farm performance data also.
6. **Provide ongoing support** through (short) visits, phone consultations, membership of a WhatsApp group, emails, invitations to events etc.
7. **Facilitate farmer-to-farmer learning.** Farmer groups help farmers to identify solutions and solve problems, while allowing farmers to support one another. Consider forming a group of "like minded" farmers to discuss more sustainable farming practices or include the topic in existing group discussions.
8. **Prepare for a long-time horizon:** it may be a number of years before there are measurable environmental and economic outcomes. Also, tackle the adoption of one or two mitigation practices at a time...avoid identifying a list of actions to be taken.
9. Familiarise yourself with currently available **rewards and incentives**, available from the Government/ EU or from the marketplace. Be able to highlight what is required of the farmer to avail themselves of these.
10. Consider what else you can do to **create an enabling environment** that facilitates the farmer taking climate action.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

How can an advisor best support a farmer as they implement climate mitigation and adaptation measures? A useful first step would be to increase the farmer's awareness of the need for climate action, followed by the completion of a GHG audit, to establish the baseline farm GHG emissions. Once the audit is completed, the advisor and farmer can then identify areas for action and agree an action plan. Following this, it will be up to the farmer to implement the chosen actions, and for the advisor to continue to support the farmer in their transition. It is likely that advisors will work with farmers at different stages of the innovation-decision process (Rogers, 2003; Figure 1) and that the advisor's role will change depending on where the farmer is during the process. Advisors will make an impact through a combination of advisory activities, focusing on relevant and user-friendly content, which stimulates farmer learning and motivates their decision to apply new knowledge.

The Climate Farm Demo Top Tips for advisors supporting farmers in the uptake of climate mitigation and adaptation measures are listed below:

1. **Get to know the farmers you are trying to influence.** A range of factors, such as age, access to finance and attitude towards risk, impact the willingness of farmers to change their farming practices. Don't forget the personal touch – make the connection with the farmer, and their family. And most importantly, listen to the farmer's arguments, fears and wishes.
2. **Highlight the positives** including good practices and the progress made by the farmer, without being afraid of calling out the areas for improvement.
3. **Keep it simple.** Farmers need to know that the recommended solutions are backed up by science, that the new approaches work to reduce GHG emissions...but don't necessarily need to know all the scientific details.
4. **Frame your messages carefully**, highlighting the benefits to the farmer (profitability, productivity, work-life balance) of adopting climate mitigation or adaptation measures. Farmers tend to implement climate-beneficial measures due to other farm-related benefits.
5. **Always prepare before meeting with the farmer.** Use available benchmarking tools/ GHG assessment tools to understand the farm's current GHG emissions profile. Review other available farm performance data also.

6. **Provide ongoing support** through (short) visits, phone consultations, membership of a WhatsApp group, emails, invitations to events etc.
7. **Facilitate farmer-to-farmer learning.** Farmer groups help farmers to identify solutions and solve problems, while allowing farmers to support one another. Consider forming a group of “like minded” farmers to discuss more sustainable farming practices or include the topic in existing group discussions.
8. **Prepare for a long-time horizon:** it may be a number of years before there are measurable environmental and economic outcomes. Also, tackle the adoption of one or two mitigation practices at a time and avoid identifying a list of actions to be taken.
9. Familiarise yourself with currently available **rewards and incentives**, available from Government/ EU or from the marketplace. Be able to highlight what is required of the farmer to avail of these.
10. Consider what else you can do to **create an enabling environment** that facilitates the farmer taking climate action.

PHOTOS

Figure 1: Rogers' Innovation Decision Process

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #92**SHORT TITLE IN NATIVE LANGUAGE**

Comment réduire les émissions de méthane des ruminants ? D'après Roques et al., 2024

SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH

How Can Methane Emissions from Ruminants be Reduced? (Roques et al., 2024)

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

All climatic zones

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Enteric methane
2. Methane emission reduction
3. Feed additives

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

Dairy cattle, Beef cattle, Sheep, Goat

THEMATIC AREA

Additives for reducing enteric methane emissions

SUMMARY FOR PRACTITIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Le méthane des ruminants provient de la digestion des aliments dans le rumen, où des microbes spécialisés (les méthanogènes) transforment certains composants de la ration en méthane, qui est ensuite rejeté dans l'air par éructation. Le méthane éructé constitue une des principales sources de gaz à effet de serre en agriculture. Il est donc essentiel de trouver des solutions pour limiter ces émissions sans compromettre la production et le bien-être des animaux.

Les stratégies existantes pour réduire les émissions de méthane

Plusieurs leviers d'action sont scientifiquement documentés et efficaces pour réduire le méthane émis par les ruminants :

L'alimentation : modifier la ration peut influencer la production de méthane. Par exemple, introduire certains additifs comme les matières grasses ou les tannins, ou privilégier des aliments plus digestibles peut permettre de réduire les émissions.

La sélection génétique : il existe des variations individuelles dans la production de méthane des animaux qui permettent de sélectionner des animaux qui émettent moins. Cela pourrait, à long terme, permettre de réduire les émissions à l'échelle du troupeau.

Les compléments alimentaires anti-méthane : certains compléments bloquent directement la production de méthane dans le rumen. Ces solutions sont très efficaces mais nécessitent une distribution régulière dans l'alimentation, ce qui peut être compliqué dans les élevages au pâturage.

Les nouvelles technologies : des travaux sont en cours sur des vaccins ciblant les microbes producteurs de méthane ou des dispositifs captant le méthane directement à la sortie du nez des animaux. Ces approches sont encore expérimentales mais pourraient offrir des solutions complémentaires dans le futur.

Quels défis pour l'avenir ?

La réduction des émissions de méthane ne doit pas compromettre la rentabilité des élevages ni leur rôle dans la production alimentaire mondiale. La faisabilité des solutions varie selon les systèmes d'élevage, les conditions économiques et les infrastructures disponibles. Pour avoir un impact réel à grande échelle, il faudra combiner plusieurs stratégies et

s'assurer qu'elles restent accessibles aux éleveurs et pratique dans leur utilisation.

En conclusion, la lutte contre les émissions de méthane passe par une meilleure gestion de l'alimentation, la sélection génétique, l'utilisation de compléments alimentaires et l'innovation technologique. Ces efforts doivent s'accompagner de politiques de soutien pour encourager les pratiques durables tout en maintenant la durabilité, y compris économique, des exploitations agricoles.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Methane (CH₄) comes from the digestion of feed in the rumen, where specialized microbes (methanogens) convert certain components of the diet into methane, which is then eructated into the air. Eructated methane is one of the main sources of greenhouse gases in agriculture.

There are several scientifically documented and effective ways to reduce the methane emitted by ruminants:

- **Feed:** Changing the ruminant diet can influence CH₄ production. For example, introducing feed supplements such as fats or tannins or using more digestible feed can reduce methane emissions.
- **Genetic selection:** There are individual variations in methane production among animals, making it possible to select those that emit less methane. In the long term, this could help reduce herd-wide emissions.
- **Feed additives:** These prevent CH₄ production in the rumen. While highly effective, they require regular distribution in the feed, which can be challenging for grazing livestock.
- **New technologies:** Research is underway on vaccines targeting methane-producing microbes and devices that capture methane directly from the animals' noses. These approaches are still experimental but could provide complementary solutions in the future.

Reducing CH₄ emissions must not compromise the profitability of livestock farming or its role in global food production. The feasibility of solutions varies depending on farming systems, economic conditions, and available infrastructure. To have a real large-scale impact, multiple solutions must be combined while ensuring they remain accessible and practical for farmers.

In conclusion, reducing methane emissions requires better feed management, genetic selection, the use of feed additives, and technological innovation. This must be supported by policies that promote sustainable practices while preserving the economic sustainability of farms.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

Roques et al. published a comprehensive paper in 2024 in the *Annual Review of Animal Biosciences* ([link](#)) titled: “Recent Advances in Enteric Methane Mitigation and the Long Road to Sustainable Ruminant Production.”

Main Strategies and Their Mechanisms for Reducing Methane Emissions in Ruminants (see *Figure 1*)

- (a) Herd Level: Methane emissions are reduced by breeding low-emitting animals, either through direct selection or genomic selection based on methane-related genetic traits.
- (b) Dietary Strategies: Methane is reduced by increasing digestibility, accelerating passage rates, or bypassing the rumen to limit nutrient availability for microbes.
- (c) Rumen-Level Strategies: Mitigation occurs by inhibiting hydrogen-producing microbes, shifting the methanogenesis substrate, or directly inhibiting methanogens.
- (d) Targeted Strategies: These approaches reduce methane emissions by inhibiting key enzymes in the methanogenesis pathway or directly affecting methanogens' viability.
[Abbreviations: CNSL – cashew nutshell liquid; 3-NOP – 3-nitrooxypropanol]

The individual variation in enteric methane emissions observed among animals under identical feeding and management conditions suggests the potential for breeding low-emission cattle and sheep. To achieve this, animals with genetic potential for lower methane emissions must be identified and selected (Figure 1a). The heritability of methane production (0 = no impact, 1 = extreme impact) ranges from 0.13 to 0.29 in sheep and 0.11 to 0.45 in dairy cattle.

Dietary Strategies and Methane Mitigation

Dietary strategies modulate methanogenesis in two ways:

1. By influencing the production of substrates used by methanogens

2. By directly affecting methanogens themselves (Figure 1b,c)

The key dietary factors affecting the rumen ecosystem include:

- Feed digestibility (positively correlated with methane emissions)
- Fermentation products
- Rumen pH

Replacing carbohydrates with lipids in ruminant diets effectively reduces absolute methane emissions. However, dietary and management strategies at the herd level provide an average mitigation effect of 18%, while the global reduction remains much lower (<10%) due to adoption rates and economic challenges.

Most strategies reduce the emission intensity of ruminant-based products, but overall emissions would decrease only if ruminant numbers were reduced. In contrast, strategies that specifically target methanogens and the methanogenic pathway (Figure 1d) have been shown to effectively reduce emissions, often with limited negative effects on the rumen microbial ecosystem. These strategies include feed additives, some of which are now commercially available in certain countries.

PHOTOS

Thomson, L. et al. 2019
 doi:10.1016/j.arscn.2019.100229-101
 Annual Reviews

Figure 1: A short extract summarising the various levers for action presented by the authors (in the text above)

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)**Title/Description**

“Recent Advances in Enteric Methane Mitigation and the Long Road to Sustainable Ruminant Production” in Annual Review of Animal Biosciences, Volume 12, 2024

URL:

<https://www.annualreviews.org/content/journals/10.1146/annurev-animal-021022-024931>

PRACTICE ABSTRACT #100**SHORT TITLE IN ENGLISH**

GEEP - An Environmental Assessment Tool for Pig Farming in France

COUNTRY AND CLIMATIC ZONE

France, temperate climate

CONTACT

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3 BENEFITS OF THE PRACTICE

1. Environmental assessment of pig farming
2. Good environmental practices
3. Decision-making tool

PRODUCTION SYSTEM

Pig farming – all production system

THEMATIC AREAS/SECTOR

- Pigs sector
- Manure storage and spreading
- Energy management
- Herd management

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

Depuis 2014, l'IFIP (institut technique de la filière porcine) met à disposition des éleveurs de porcs français, l'outil de calcul GEEP, pour évaluer les performances environnementales de leur atelier. GEEP c'est aussi un réseau qui regroupe plus de 900 éleveurs porcins et environ 130 conseillers. Le bilan

environnemental s'appuie sur 9 indicateurs quantitatifs portant sur les consommations de ressources naturelles (eau et énergie), les rejets (azote et phosphore), les émissions gazeuses (ammoniac et gaz à effet de serre) et la production de déchets. Ces indicateurs sont calculés avec les flux environnementaux de l'élevage divisés par les kilogrammes de porc générés sur l'élevage (ex : kg de NH₃/ kg de porc produit).

Pour les émissions de gaz à effets de serre, le périmètre prend en compte l'ensemble du cycle de production de porc dans une approche par ACV (analyse de cycle de vie), l'indicateur est alors exprimé par kg de poids vif. Ce type d'indicateur permet aux éleveurs de se comparer à d'autres élevages de même orientation et de se positionner par rapport à des références collectives. GEEP est connecté à la base nationale de données technico-économiques gérée par l'IFIP, ce qui représente un gain de temps pour la saisie des données individuelles et un gage de robustesse de l'information. Cet outil est sensible à de nombreux leviers de réduction d'émissions de GES. L'éleveur peut renseigner la formulation de l'aliment consommé en choisissant les matières premières et leur origine, pour calculer au plus juste l'empreinte carbone de celui-ci. Il intègre de nombreuses bonnes pratiques sur la chaîne de gestion des effluents : fréquence d'évacuation des effluents au bâtiment, différentes modalités de stockage, méthanisation... Les résultats prennent également en compte les performances techniques de chaque stade physiologique. GEEP est un outil complet pour accompagner l'éleveur dans une démarche d'amélioration continue.

SUMMARY FOR PRACTICIONERS ON THE MAIN FINDING(S)/INNOVATIVE SOLUTION(S) – IN ENGLISH

Since 2014, IFIP (the French technical institute for the pig industry) has been providing French pig farmers with the GEEP calculation tool to assess the environmental performance of their workshops. GEEP is also a network of over 900 pig farmers and around 130 advisors. The environmental balance sheet is based on nine quantitative indicators covering the consumption of natural resources (water and energy), emissions (nitrogen and phosphorus), gaseous emissions (ammonia and greenhouse gases), and waste production. These indicators are calculated using the environmental flows from the farm divided by the kilograms of pigs produced on the farm (e.g., kg of NH₃ per kg of pigs produced).

For greenhouse gas emissions, the scope considers the entire pig production cycle using an LCA (life cycle assessment) approach, with the indicator expressed per kg of live weight. This type of indicator enables farmers to compare their performance with other farms in the same sector

and collective benchmarks. GEEP is connected to the national technical-economic database managed by IFIP, which saves time when entering individual data and ensures the robustness of the information.

This tool is sensitive to several levers for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Farmers can enter the formulation of the feed they use, selecting the raw feedstuffs and their origin to calculate the feed's carbon footprint as accurately as possible. It incorporates several best practices in the effluent management chain, including the frequency of effluent evacuation from buildings, different storage methods, and methanization. The results also consider the technical performance of each physiological stage. GEEP is a comprehensive tool designed to support farmers in their efforts toward continuous improvement.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN NATIVE LANGUAGE

En France, la décarbonation prend une place plus importante en production porcine, du fait de la dynamique autour de l'affichage environnemental des produits de consommation, et du fait du Label Bas Carbone initié par le Ministère de la Transition écologique. L'affichage officialise le bilan carbone des produits porcins auprès des consommateurs et génère de fait des questions pour l'étape élevage qui contribue largement à cet impact final ; le Label Bas Carbone donne des perspectives d'une rémunération des efforts réalisés par les éleveurs pour réduire leurs émissions de gaz à effet de serre, sous réserve d'une méthode sectorielle validée pour l'élevage porcine par le MTE.

Accompagner les élevages pour atteindre les objectifs nationaux bas-carbone

La stratégie nationale bas-carbone (SNBC) fixe en France des objectifs de réduction de 46 % des émissions de gaz à effet de serre pour l'agriculture.

Des simulations montrent qu'un élevage naisseur-engraisseur moyen de 250 truies pourrait réduire ses émissions de GES de 2 à 25% à l'échelle du cycle de vie du porc, en fonction des leviers choisis. Cela représenterait quelques dizaines à plusieurs centaines de tonnes de CO2 évitées par an.

Pour permettre une rémunération de ces efforts, une méthode Label Bas Carbone a été construite pour les élevages porcins. Elle s'appuie largement sur la méthode d'évaluation de GEEP en y apportant plus de précisions pour évaluer les émissions de gaz à effet de serre de deux postes.

Elle prend en compte la formulation des aliments qu'ils soient achetés ou fabriqués à la ferme, et permet de prendre en compte l'effet de la

substitution de MP importées liées à la déforestation, de la valorisation des co-produits.

Elle aborde de façon plus détaillée l'étape de méthanisation éventuelles des effluents avec les différents modèles (méthanisation psychrophile, co-génération, injection, unité en autonomie ou collective).

La sensibilité de GEEP aux différents leviers d'atténuation au changement climatique en fait un outil pertinent pour soutenir les projets de décarbonation des ateliers porcins. Ainsi, il est retenu dans deux projets européens (Climate farm demo et Climate smart advisors) qui visent, sur une durée de 6 ans à accompagner des fermes pilotes dans l'élaboration de leur plan d'atténuation et d'adaptation au changement climatique, dans un objectif de démonstration et de massification sur le terrain.

GEEP, un outil en constante évolution pour répondre aux besoins des utilisateurs

GEEP évolue dans ses bases de références et les règles de calculs des émissions gazeuses pour être au plus près des dernières actualisations. Il tient également compte des besoins des utilisateurs et offre depuis 2023 la possibilité de renseigner la formulation détaillée de l'aliment consommé afin d'être au plus près des pratiques réelles de l'élevage, et également l'impact carbone de l'aliment consommé acheté.

Pour diffuser l'information et appréhender les attentes des utilisateurs, plusieurs temps d'échanges sont mis en place chaque année avec le réseau de conseillers.

LONGER DESCRIPTION – IN ENGLISH

In France, decarbonization is becoming increasingly important in pork production due to the environmental labeling of consumer products and the Low Carbon Label launched by the French Ministry for Ecological Transition. The Low Carbon Label offers the prospect of remuneration for pig farmers' efforts to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions, provided they follow a sector-specific method validated for pig farming by the Ministry.

Supporting Pig Farms in Achieving National Low-Carbon Objectives

France's national low-carbon strategy (SNBC) sets a target of reducing greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture by 46%.

Simulations show that an average farrow-to-finish farm with 250 sows could reduce its greenhouse gas emissions by 2% to 25% over the pig's life cycle,

depending on the mitigation measures implemented. This reduction would amount to several dozen to several hundred tonnes of CO₂ avoided per year.

To reward these efforts, a Low Carbon Label method has been developed specifically for pig farms. It is largely based on the GEEP evaluation method, with a more detailed assessment of greenhouse gas emissions in two key areas:

- **Feed formulation:** Whether purchased or produced on the farm, this method allows for the substitution of imported raw materials linked to deforestation and the processing of co-products.
- **Effluent methanization:** A more detailed assessment is conducted, considering different models such as psychrophilic methanization, co-generation, injection, and autonomous or collective units.

GEEP's sensitivity to various climate change mitigation levers makes it a valuable tool for supporting the decarbonization of pig farms. As a result, GEEP has been selected for two European projects—Climate Farm Demo and Climate Smart Advisors—which, over six years, aim to assist pilot farms in developing climate change mitigation and adaptation plans. These efforts will serve as demonstrations for large-scale implementation in the field.

GEEP: A Constantly Evolving Tool to Meet User Needs

GEEP's reference databases and calculation rules for gaseous emissions are continuously updated to incorporate the latest developments. It also adapts to user needs. Since 2023, it has allowed farmers to enter the detailed formulation of the feed used, ensuring alignment with actual on-farm practices and enabling precise calculations of the carbon impact of purchased feed.

To disseminate information and understand user expectations, several meetings are organized annually with the network of advisors.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Support for Specifications and Eco-Design Initiatives in Supply Chains

The list of specifications recognizing GEEP for monitoring environmental and collective performance is growing steadily, and the tool is also being used in several eco-design initiatives.

Outlook

The **Label Bas Carbone** method for pig farming is currently under review by the French Ministry for Ecological Transition. In 2025, the new version of

GEEP for the methanization component will be finalized, ensuring full compatibility with the calculation rules associated with the draft LBC pork method.

To meet user needs, **IFIP and IDELE** are working on integrating GEEP with **CAP'2ER**, the environmental assessment tool designed for cattle and poultry, to support a whole-farm approach.

Collective data from GEEP will soon be more widely disseminated through a summary brochure, following validation by a newly formed strategic committee.

PHOTOS

Photo 1: GEEP

ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIAL(S)

Description/Title

Learn more about GEEP

URL:

<https://geep.ifip.asso.fr/>

Chapter 5

Annexes

5.1 Guidelines

What are Practice Abstracts (PAs)

Practice Abstracts are innovative, practice-oriented solutions for farmers, foresters, advisors and rural communities.

The 'practice abstracts' must be clear and concise as well as be attractive and relevant for practice. They should be drafted from the view to make them well understandable to the end-user and focus on those elements that most interest him/her. Typical scientific language is to be avoided. The focus should be on the needs/objectives of the Climate Farm Demo and its practical outcomes/recommendations. Details on the precise activities/measurements are less important than the final practical results and recommendations.

Climate Farm Demo Practice Abstracts (PAs) – batch 1

The first batch of 100 Practice Abstracts must be finalized and submitted by the end of March 2025. To enhance visibility and accessibility, in addition to being uploaded to the EU CAP Network, Climate Farm Demo will feature a dedicated section on its website. www.climatefarmdemo.eu. Unlike static PDF documents, each Practice Abstract will be presented as an individual landing page, allowing for automatic translation into all project languages and English to reach broader audiences.

To streamline navigation and organization, the Practice Abstracts will be categorized into the following clusters: **Adaptation and Mitigation Measures, Pilot Demo Farms, Living Labs, Rewarding Mechanisms, MRV Tools, and Cross-Cutting Topics**. Dedicated templates have been developed for each cluster, enabling better filtering and ensuring end-users can easily access relevant content.

Steps for writing and submitting PAs

- 1. Assigning Tasks:**
 - o Work Package Leaders (WPLs): Responsible for drafting PAs related to their work package.
 - o National Coordinators (NCs): Draft PAs and assign Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs) to write specific PAs.
 - o Thematic Leaders (TLs): Draft PAs related to their thematic areas.
- 2. Download the Template:**
 - o Select the appropriate PA template based on your topic and cluster.
 - o Please **DO NOT** fill in the template directly on SharePoint, but rather download it first and then fill it in. You can find the templates [here](#).
- 3. Update the Monitoring Table:**
 - o Insert relevant information into the provided monitoring table [here](#).
- 4. Draft the PA:**
 - o Fill in the chosen template with accurate and concise information.
 - o Ensure the draft is completed by **February 15th**.
- 5. Submit the PA:**
 - o Upload the finalized template to the dedicated folder [here](#).
- 6. Please save and upload the document in .docx format (Word)**

- Please rename the document accordingly – **CFD – PA – #X – Title of the PA in English**
 - o Mark the corresponding checkbox in the monitoring table [here](#) to confirm submission.
- 7. Upload the photos [here](#), (create a folder for your dedicated PA)**
 - 8. Please upload photos in .jpg, .jpeg or .png formats**
 - 9. Review and Dissemination:**
 - o WPL will review and revise all submitted PAs.
 - 10. Final versions will be uploaded to the EU CAP Network and featured on the Climate Farm Demo website.**

Sections in the template - mandatory

All sections marked with * are mandatory to complete.

Title

Provide a self-explanatory title that shortly summarises the challenge/opportunity and the project result(s) that address(es)/seize(s) it/them and are relevant for the practitioners. The title should be written in both native language and English, and the maximum character limits specified in the templates (255 characters, including spaces) are strictly adhered to.

3 Benefits of the Practice

Please insert 3 key benefits of the practice (keywords) to improve filtering and enhance the visibility of your practice. Including relevant keywords helps categorize the content effectively, making it easier for users to find and access, and amplifies its reach to a broader audience.

Summary for Practitioners on the Main Finding(s)/Innovative Solution(s)

The most important part of your PA is Summary for Practitioners on the Main Finding(s)/Innovative Solution(s). This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/foresters/other end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, benefits, productivity, etc.). Presenting research results in scientific language, which does not respond to real needs of the practitioners, should be avoided.

Summary should consist of:

- **Objective(s):** what challenge(s)/opportunity(ies) does the project address/seize that are relevant for the practitioners/end-users?
- **Result(s)** of the project related to what new knowledge/innovative solution(s) have been developed that solve the challenge(s)/seize the opportunity(ies).
- **Practical implications/recommendations:** how can the practitioners make use of the results/outcomes in practice? What would be the main costs/benefits to the end-users if the generated new knowledge / innovative solution(s) is(are) implemented? etc.
- **Target Audience:** Specify who can benefit from the practice (e.g., farmers, advisors).

To ensure the text is presented accurately, it is mandatory to write the summary in both the native language and English. We recommend using [DeepL Translate](#), *The world's most accurate translator*, for translating into English. However, we strongly advise reviewing the translated version to ensure its accuracy.

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Please ensure that the **maximum character limits** specified in the templates (2,000 characters, including spaces) are strictly adhered to.

Photos/Images

To make your PA more engaging and avoid plain text, please upload photos and images that best represent the topic you are writing about. You can upload them by creating a subfolder in the dedicated folder [pa#x](#) (rename the subfolder as # and the number of your PA as presented in the example for #1 and #2) and upload the high-resolution images there for better quality.

Sections in the template – optional

Longer summary for the Climate Farm Demo website

The Climate Farm Demo website provides an opportunity for a more in-depth exploration of your findings. While the 2,000-character summary is required, we believe this length may be too limiting to fully capture the details of your work. Therefore, although not mandatory, we suggest you provide a longer version of your summary, with a maximum of 4,000 characters (including spaces). This additional text will allow end-users to dive deeper into the topic, and it will give you the space to elaborate on your results, recommendations, and any other relevant information that can further enhance their understanding.

Longer summary should be submitted in both native language and English, allowing your PA to be automatically translated to all project languages.

Additional Dissemination and Exploitation Material(s)

Provide title/description and URL link to additional materials which are useful and attractive for practitioners (e.g., link to relevant websites, social media, videos, pictures, pdf files, other dissemination materials).

Although it is not mandatory, we highly recommend sharing additional materials with end-users. Many partners have already produced video content and webinars, which is available on our FarmDemo YouTube channel. These videos can further enrich the understanding of your topic and provide a more engaging experience for the audience.

Whom should I contact if I have some questions?

For any questions or concerns, please contact the person who assigned you to write the PA. For all the other partners – please contact saidora.colic@biosense.rs in case you have any questions and/or concerns.

PROJECT NAME – Climate Farm Demo
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5.2 Website Feature

Visit www.climatefarmdemo.eu and navigate to the 'Resources' section, then select 'Practice Abstracts'.

The Practice Abstracts are organized into **six thematic clusters**, each representing a key topic area. Selecting a topic reveals related content. *This page is currently under construction.*

Filter

Enter a key word to search

Country

Thematic area

Search **Reset**

To help navigate the extensive collection, Practice Abstracts can be searched and filtered by **keyword, country, and thematic area.**

Increasing organic matter by intercrops

Italy Cool Temperate Dry

Benefits of the practice

1. Prevention of soil erosion, increasing organic matter
2. Carbon sequestration
3. Weed control

Production system

Conventional/organic

Thematic Area

Intercropping

Summary for practitioners on the main finding(s)/Innovative solution(s)

The use of intercrops has changed over the years; their earlier function on Polish farms was to produce fodder for animals. Today, their primary function is to provide protection against wind and water erosion, as well as to enrich the soil with organic matter.

Contact

Paweł Górecki

Each Practice Abstract will follow this format: it includes the **country, climatic zone, benefits of the practice, production system, thematic area, a short summary (up to 2000 characters), an extended description accessible via a dropdown menu, and the author's contact information.** Where applicable, both summaries and extended descriptions will be available in original languages.